

The periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange equation

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Dedicated to the memory of my father Erik Bonde Jensen

The Author thanks Prof. dr. hab. Andrzej Nowakowski.

ABSTRACT. We intent in this thesis to investigate the periodic qualities of the Euler-Lagrange equations, $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \right) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$, under some conditions for L . The conditions on L are basically that L is separated with respect to x and \dot{x} , that L is strictly convex with respect to x , that L is strictly concave with respect to \dot{x} , that L is autonomous and that L satisfy some growth condition. The more precise conditions follow later.

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Preface

We will prove a theorem regarding the periodic qualities of the Euler-Lagrange equations, $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \right) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$, under some assumptions for L . The assumptions on L are basically that L is strictly convex with respect to x , that L is strictly concave with respect to \dot{x} , that L is autonomous and that L satisfies some growth condition. The more precise assumptions follow later.

The theorem is basically that the Euler-Lagrange equations is always periodic.

1. The philosophy behind this thesis

The mathematics was first developed using nonstandard analytical and geometrical considerations. The author would have liked to prove the theorem using nonstandard analysis and geometry. This would have elucidated and simplified the proof. The insufficient development of nonstandard analysis and its geometrical uses seems to make such a proof not possible and/or feasible. The author would like to propose the development of a mathematical foundation and methods of analysis using nonstandard analysis and geometry.

Part 1

A a new periodicity theorem

CHAPTER 1

The Euler-Lagrange equation

With the work of Euler (c. 1742) and Lagrange (c. 1755) the theory of calculus of variations emerged in a more systematic form [1, V.I Arnold, Mathematical Methods of Classical Mechanics, p145].

The Euler-Lagrange equation is of fundamental importance in the classical theory of calculus of variations. This is seen by the following theorem from [2, Jurgen Jost and Xianqing Li-Jost, Calculus of Variations , p6] :

THEOREM 1. *let $L \in C^2([a, b] \times \mathbf{R}^d \times \mathbf{R}^d)$, and let $x \in C^2([a, b], \mathbf{R}^d)$ be a minimizer of*

$$(0.1) \quad I(u) = \int_a^b L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt$$

among all functions with prescribed boundary values $x(a)$ and $x(b)$. Then x is a solution of the following system of second order ordinary differential equations, the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$(0.2) \quad \frac{d}{dt}(L_{\dot{x}}(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t))) - L_x(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = 0$$

In this thesis we confine ourself to study the Euler-Lagrange equations for 1 dimension, $d = 1$. The generalization of the results of this thesis to $d \in \mathbf{N}_+$ is not difficult. We do this to simplify our notation and to concentrate on the important ideas.

We can also formulate the Euler-Lagrange equation as $\frac{d}{dt}(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t))) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x}(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = 0$. This is the preferred formulation in this thesis. This formulation is preferred because its hints at the non standard analytic roots of the derivatives.

CHAPTER 2

Languages and expressions

1. The languages we will use

In mechanics L is called the *Lagrange function* or the *Lagrangian*. In this thesis we will call L the Lagrange function [1, V.I Arnold, Mathematical Methods of Classical Mechanics, p60].

2. Some Definitions and some basic expressions.

We use the dot notation, ".", to denote differentials of t . e.g. $\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{dt}$.

We have that $t \in R$. The variable t typically starts at $t = a$ and ends at $t = b$ where $b > a$ and $a, b \in R$.

The function denoted by x is a function of t . We have that $x \in C^3([a, b])$. The derivative w.r.t. t is denoted \dot{x} or $\frac{dx}{dt}$. We have that $\dot{x} \in C^2([a, b])$.

We let the lagrange function $L \in C^3(R \times R)$. We further put some assumptions on the lagrange function L . The assumptions are:

- (1) L is autonomous w.r.t to t . That is, L does not depend on t . This condition is clearly necessary for the proposed main theorem to be true.
- (2) L is separable w.r.t x and \dot{x} . A function is separable w.r.t some variables if it can be expressed as a sum of functions that does not depend on variables contained in the other functions. L can be expressed as the sum of the two functions h and g where $h \in C^3(R)$, $g \in C^3(R)$. h is a function of x and g is a function of \dot{x} . The expression is $L = h(x) + g(\dot{x})$.
- (3) $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} > 0$. Having $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} > 0$ also makes g strictly convex w.r.t. \dot{x} .
- (4) $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$. Having $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$ also makes h strictly concave w.r.t x .
- (5) L satisfy growth condition 3 as stated in the appendix, proposition 11. The condition on L takes the form $g(\dot{x}) \rightarrow \infty$ for $\dot{x} \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and $h(x) \rightarrow -\infty$ for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. The growth

condition ensures that there exists a $\dot{x} \in R$ such that $g'(\dot{x}) = 0$ and there exists a $x \in R$ such that $h'(x) = 0$.

REMARK 1. That our L is separable w.r.t x and \dot{x} and can be expressed as $L = h(x) + g(\dot{x})$ gives that $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$.

REMARK 2. A function f w.r.t x , where $f \in C^2(R)$, that is convex or concave can have intervals where $\frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} = 0$, these intervals are illustrated in red on the figure 1 below.

FIGURE 1

REMARK 3. A function f w.r.t x , where $f \in C^2(R)$, that is strictly convex or strictly concave. f can have points where $\frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} = 0$, these points are illustrated in red on the figure 2 below.

FIGURE 2

REMARK 4. A function f w.r.t x , where $f \in C^2(R)$, that has $\frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} > 0$ is also strictly convex. If f has $\frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} < 0$ then is f also strictly concave. In both cases has f no points where $\frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} = 0$, this is illustrated on figure 3 below.

FIGURE 3

We denote $R_{x\dot{x}}^2$ as the set of all points (x, \dot{x}) where $x = x(t)$ and $\dot{x} = \dot{x}(t)$ for some t and x . At t has both x and \dot{x} to be defined. $R_{x\dot{x}}^2$ will contain exactly all the points in the R^2 space.

If the function x is a minimizer of $\int_a^b L(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt$ then will the Euler-Lagrange solution be the Euler-Lagrange function x for $L(x, \dot{x})$ with $x = x(t)$ and $\dot{x} = \dot{x}(t)$ and where $t \in [a, b]$.

An Euler-Lagrange curve $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ is a parameter curve in t for some Euler-Lagrange function $L(x, \dot{x})$ with $x = x(t)$ and $\dot{x} = \dot{x}(t)$ and where $t \in [a, b]$. The Euler-Lagrange equations are satisfied for x along this curve.

We see from proposition 4 below that Euler-Lagrange solutions for $L(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 - \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2$ exist and that they are periodic in t . The solution x has the orbit $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t in the set $R_{x\dot{x}}^2$. Figure 4 illustrates the lagrange function $L(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 - \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2$ as the green surface. The blue curve illustrates the Euler-Lagrange curve with initial condition $x(0) = 0$ and $\dot{x}(0) = 1$ and where $t \in [0, 2\pi]$.

FIGURE 4

The first order partial derivatives of L are: $\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$. We have that $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \in C^3(R)$, $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} \in C^2(R)$. and that $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ is a function of x and $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$ is a function of \dot{x} .

We have from theorem 1 the Euler-Lagrange equation for $t \in [a, b]$ and we use $\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$ to get:

$$(2.1) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} (\dot{x}(t)) \right) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (x(t))$$

We define p as a function in t that along an Euler-Lagrange curve is:

$$(2.2) \quad p(t) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} (\dot{x}(t))$$

We define $\tilde{p} \in C^2(R)$ as a function of \dot{x} . It is the function:

$$\tilde{p}(\dot{x}) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} (\dot{x})$$

We substitute \tilde{p} into the Euler-Lagrange equation along an Euler-Lagrange curve and get another expression of the Euler-Lagrange equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} (x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \right) &= \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} (x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \iff \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} (\dot{x}(t)) \right) &= \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (x(t)) \iff \\ \frac{d}{dt} \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (x(t)) \iff \end{aligned}$$

$$(2.3) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (x(t))$$

We define $\hat{p} \in C^2(R)$ as a function of x . It is the function:

$$\hat{p}(x) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} (x)$$

We see that along an Euler-Lagrange curve will we have $\frac{d}{dt}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = \hat{p}(x(t))$ for $t \in [a, b]$, this equation is an Euler-Lagrange condition. We write the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$(2.4) \quad \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t))$$

The set V is defined to contain all points $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ where x is any Euler-Lagrange curve fulfilling some assumptions. The set V is the graph of all Euler-Lagrange curve fulfilling some assumptions.

$R_{\dot{x}x}^2$ is as we remember the set of all points (\dot{x}, x) where $x \in R$ and $\dot{x} \in R$. We denote $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}^2$ as the set of all points (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) where $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t))$ for some L and t . At t has both x , \dot{x} , \tilde{p} and \hat{p} to be defined. $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}^2$ will contain exactly all the points in the R^2 space.

The set U is defined to contain all points (\dot{x}, \hat{p}) belonging to $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}^2$ that is obtained by mapping the set V using $(\dot{x}, \hat{p}) = (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}(\dot{x})) = (\dot{x}, \hat{p}(x)) = (\dot{x}, \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x))$.

See the appendix chapter **6**.

CHAPTER 3

Rewriting the Euler-Lagrange equation

PROPOSITION 1. *Let L follow the assumptions 1-5 then $(\dot{\hat{p}}(x(t))) = (\dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)))$ is an Euler-Lagrange equations in the set U along an Euler-Lagrange curve.*

We know that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x})$ where $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} \in C^2(R)$ and that $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \dot{x}^2}(\dot{x}) > 0$. We have that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}) \in C^2(R)$ and that $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}(\dot{x})}{\partial \dot{x}} > 0$. We see that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x})$ is an increasing function of \dot{x} . $\tilde{p} = \tilde{p}(\dot{x})$ will therefor have an inverse function $\dot{x} = \dot{x}(\tilde{p})$ and the inverse function will be differential and have the differential $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p})$. We know that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}) = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x})}$ at any point (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) for the function and its inverse function. We have

$$(0.1) \quad \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x})} = \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p})$$

or along a parameter curve

$$(0.2) \quad \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t))}$$

We know that $\hat{p}(x) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x)$ where $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \in C^2(R)$ and that $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x^2}(x) < 0$. We have that $\hat{p}(x) \in C^3(R)$ and that $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) < 0$. We see that $\hat{p}(x)$ is an decreasing function of x . $\hat{p} = \hat{p}(x)$ will therefor have an inverse function $x = x(\hat{p})$ and the inverse function will be differential and have the differential $\frac{\partial x}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p})$. We know that $\frac{\partial x}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}) = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))}$ at any point (x, \hat{p}) for a function and its inverse function. We have

$$(0.3) \quad \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x)} = \frac{\partial x}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p})$$

or along a parameter curve

$$(0.4) \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(x(t))) = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))}$$

We have along any curve:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \frac{d \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t))}{d\dot{x}} \frac{d\dot{x}}{dt} \iff \\ \frac{d\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))}{dt} &= \frac{d\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))}{d\dot{x}} \frac{d\dot{x}}{dt} \iff \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \frac{d\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))}{d\dot{x}} \ddot{x}(t) \end{aligned}$$

We have from this and equation (2.4 from chapter 2) along an Euler-Lagrange curve:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \hat{p}(x(t)) \iff \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) &= \frac{d\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))}{d\dot{x}} \ddot{x}(t) \iff \\ \ddot{x}(t) &= \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{1}{\frac{d\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))}{d\dot{x}}} \iff \\ \ddot{x}(t) &= \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{aligned}$$

We have along any curve:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t)) &= \frac{\partial \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t))}{\partial x} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \iff \\ \frac{d\hat{p}(x(t))}{dt} &= \frac{\partial \hat{p}(x(t))}{\partial x} \dot{x}(t) \iff \end{aligned}$$

$$\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}(x(t))}{\partial x}$$

We express it in vector form:

$$(0.5) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$$

CHAPTER 4

Proof that every Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic

We intent in this chapter to prove a new theorem about the periodicity of the solutions of the Euler-Lagrange equation. We want to prove that every Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic with some period under assumptions 1-5 on L . We do that by proving that an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve on L is periodic. We start by studying the solutions for a particular L_A that we already know have periodic solutions. We then show that this implies that an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve for some L_B also is periodic. And then we show that this implies that some arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve for some L_C also is periodic. Proving our theorem.

1. boundary assumptions and periodicity

The Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic with some period T if $x(t + T) = x(t)$ for all $t \in R$. This will be fulfilled if $x(a) = x(a + T)$ and $\dot{x}(a) = \dot{x}(a + T)$ for some a . We see that the Euler-Lagrange curve $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t is periodic if the curve is an orbit.

We remember that $(\dot{x}, \dot{p}) = (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}(\dot{x})) = (\dot{x}, \hat{p}(x)) = (\dot{x}, \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x))$.

If the Euler-Lagrange curve $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t is periodic then is also the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(t))$ with parameter t an orbit.

PROPOSITION 2. *If the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(t)) = (\dot{x}(t), \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t)))$ with parameter t is an orbit then will the Euler-Lagrange curve $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t also be an orbit, and therefor periodic.*

h is defined to have $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$ that tells us that $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x)$ is a bijective function of x .

If the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(t)) = (\dot{x}(t), \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t)))$ with parameter t is an orbit then will the Euler-Lagrange curve $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t also be an orbit, and therefor periodic, because $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x)$ is an bijective function of x .

2. We express Euler-Lagrange equations for L_A , L_B and L_C

We define L_A to be the Lagrange function:

$$(2.1) \quad L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$$

We see that L_A satisfy our assumption 1-5. We have $\frac{\partial L_A}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}) = \tilde{p}(\dot{x}) = \dot{x}$ and $\frac{\partial L_A}{\partial x}(x) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x) = \hat{p}(x) = -x$. We have $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}) = 1$ and $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x) = -1$ everywhere. We use and have (0.1 from chapter 3) everywhere. Along an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve on L_A will we, using (0.5 from chapter 3), have the Euler-Lagrange equations:

$$(2.2) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}(t) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \end{pmatrix}$$

We define L_B to be the Lagrange function:

$$L_B(x, \dot{x}) = g(\dot{x}) - \frac{1}{2}x^2$$

The function g is an arbitrary function fulfilling assumptions 2-3. We see that L_B satisfy our assumption 1-5. We have $\frac{\partial L_B}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} = \hat{p} = -x$. We have $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} = 1$. Along an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve with parameter t on L_B will we have the Euler-Lagrange equations:

$$(2.3) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}(t) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$$

We define L_C to be the Lagrange function:

$$(2.4) \quad L_C(x, \dot{x}) = g(\dot{x}) + h(x)$$

The function g and h are arbitrary functions fulfilling assumptions 2-4. g is the function from $L_B(x, \dot{x}) = g(\dot{x}) - \frac{1}{2}x^2$ above. We see that L_C satisfy our assumption 1-5. Along an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve with parameter t on L_C will we have the Euler-Lagrange equations:

$$(2.5) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$$

2.1. We prove that every Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ for L_A are periodic. We can deduce that every Euler-Lagrange solution belonging to the set $R_{\dot{x}\dot{x}}^2$ is periodic for $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$. The proof is given below:

PROPOSITION 3. *Let $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$. All the Euler-Lagrange functions with the Euler-Lagrange condition $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) \right) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t))$ will be periodic with $T = 2\pi$.*

We know that $\frac{\partial g_A}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}) = \dot{x}$ and $\frac{\partial h_A}{\partial x}(x) = -x$. For L_A the Euler-Lagrange condition becomes $\frac{d}{dt}(\dot{x}(t)) = -x(t)$ or $\frac{d^2}{dt^2}(x(t)) = -x(t)$. The solution to this differential equation is $x(t) = C_1 \sin(t) + C_2 \cos(t) = C \sin(A) \sin(t) + C \cos(A) \cos(t) = C \sin(A + t)$. We see that all Euler-Lagrange solutions are periodic with $T = 2\pi$.

□

PROPOSITION 4. *Let $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$. All the Euler-Lagrange curves $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ with the Euler-Lagrange condition $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) \right) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t))$ will be periodic with $T = 2\pi$.*

We have $x(t) = C \sin(A + t) \implies \dot{x}(t) = C \cos(A + t)$.

We use $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t))$ and get $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t)) = \frac{\partial h_A}{\partial x}(x(t)) = -x(t) = -C \sin(A + t)$

We have $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = (C \cos(A + t), -C \sin(A + t))$

We see that all Euler-Lagrange solutions are periodic with $T = 2\pi$.

□

2.2. We arrange the Lagrange functions L_B and L_C to elucidate the interpretation of the main theorem. The changes of L_B and L_C below, are not essential for the proof of the main theorem, but the manipulations make the proof more simple.

We look at $g(\dot{x})$, $g(\dot{x})$ is an arbitrary convex function with a $g_{\min}(\dot{x}) = b$ for $\dot{x} = d$, satisfying growth condition 3. $g(\dot{x})$ is illustrated on figure 1 below.

We can without changing any of the solutions add a constant to $g(\dot{x})$. We can choose this constant to be $-g_{\min}(d)$. This equals assuming that $g(\dot{x})$ has a $g_{\min}(\dot{x}) = 0$ for $\dot{x} = d$. This $g(\dot{x})$ is illustrated on figure 2 below.

We look at $h(x)$. $h(x)$ is an arbitrary convex function with a $h_{\max}(x) = c$ for $x = e$, satisfying growth condition 3. $h(x)$ is illustrated on figure 3 below.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

We can w.r.t x translate the Euler-Lagrange curves along with $h(x)$ without changing the form of the curves, including the periodicity property. That is we can assume that $h_{\max}(x) = c$ for $x = 0$. This $h(x)$ is illustrated on figure 4 below.

FIGURE 4

We can without changing any of the solutions add a constant to $h(x)$. We can choose this constant to be $-h_{\max}(0)$. This equals assuming that $h_{\max}(x) = 0$ for $x = 0$. This $h(x)$ is illustrated on figure 5 below.

FIGURE 5

We see that if $x > 0$ than is $\hat{p} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} < 0$, and if $x < 0$ than is $\hat{p} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} > 0$.

3. The orientation of the Euler-Lagrange trajectory

Referring to proposition 1 we have the Euler-Lagrange equation (0.5 from chapter 3) that is $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) \\ \dot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve with $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) < 0$ and $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t))) > 0$.

Because of $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))$ and $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) < 0$ will $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) > 0$ if $\dot{x}(t) < 0$ and $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) < 0$ if $\dot{x}(t) > 0$.

Because of $\dot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ and $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t))) > 0$ will $\dot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) > 0$ if $\hat{p}(x(t)) > 0$ and $\dot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) < 0$ if $\hat{p}(x(t)) < 0$.

We remember (2.4 from chapter 2) $\tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t))$.

If $\dot{x}(t) > 0$ and $\hat{p}(x(t)) > 0$ will $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) < 0$ and $\ddot{x}(t) > 0$, $\hat{p}(x(t))$ and $\tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t))$ will decrease and $\dot{x}(t)$ increase as a function of t .

If $\dot{x}(t) < 0$ and $\hat{p}(x(t)) > 0$ will $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) > 0$ and $\ddot{x}(t) > 0$, $\hat{p}(x(t))$ and $\tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t))$ will increase and $\dot{x}(t)$ increase as a function of t .

If $\dot{x}(t) > 0$ and $\hat{p}(x(t)) < 0$ will $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) < 0$ and $\ddot{x}(t) < 0$, $\hat{p}(x(t))$ and $\tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t))$ will decrease and $\dot{x}(t)$ decrease as a function of t .

If $\dot{x}(t) < 0$ and $\hat{p}(x(t)) < 0$ will $\ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) > 0$ and $\ddot{x}(t) < 0$, $\hat{p}(x(t))$ and $\tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t))$ will increase and $\dot{x}(t)$ decrease as a function of t .

We illustrate the orientation of the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{\hat{p}}(\dot{x}(t)))$ in the figure below:

4. Moving backwards along the Euler-Lagrange trajectory

Normally following a curve we move forward in t from $t = a$ to $t = b$ where $a < b$. We could also follow a curve backwards in t from $t = b$ to $t = a$ where $a < b$. We will do that in part of the main proof.

5. Proof that the Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic for L separated

THEOREM 2. *Let L satisfy assumptions 1-5. Then will every Euler-Lagrange curve be periodic.*

6. Situation A is tied to situation B for each step

We intend in this section to prove that the periodicity of an arbitrary Euler-Lagrange curve with some period length T_A in a situation A implies the periodicity with period length T_B of an Euler-Lagrange curve in a situation B . The proof uses a step by step reconstruction of the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation A to the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation B .

We follow an Euler-Lagrange curve for situation B . First we follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ forwards in t at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$ and backwards in t at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ in the \dot{x} direction.

We want to tie the situation A to situation B for each step. In situation A we also follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ forwards in t starting at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$ and backwards in t starting at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ in the \dot{x} direction.

Later on we repeat the arguments for following the Euler-Lagrange curve backwards in t at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$ and forwards in t at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ in the $-\dot{x}$ direction.

The illustration below illustrates how we follow the Euler-Lagrange curve backwards and forwards in t in our $A - B$ step by step reconstruction. The red arrow illustrates us following the Euler-Lagrange

curve backwards and the black arrow illustrates us following the Euler-Lagrange curve forwards.

Variables describing curves belonging to particular quadrants will be denoted with indexes according to the quadrant number 1,2,3 or 4. The index 0 denotes our start point.

6.1. What we already know about situation A.

PROPOSITION 5. Let $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$. We follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ forwards in t , starting at $t = 0$ at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$ in the first quadrant. We follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ backwards in t , starting at $t = \pi$ at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ in the second quadrant. Then will $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = (\tilde{p}_0 \sin(t), \tilde{p}_0 \cos(t))$ We denote variables in the first quadrant with A_1 and variables in the second quadrant with A_2 . When we have that $t_{A_1} = \pi - t_{A_2}$ will $\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ and $\tilde{p}_{A_1}(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t)) = -\tilde{p}_{A_2}(\dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}))$.

We remember (??) that is $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = (C \cos(A+t), -C \sin(A+t))$. We have the initial condition $\dot{x}_{A_1}(0) = 0$ that gives us $A = \frac{\pi}{2}$. We have $\dot{x}(t) = C \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} + t) = C \sin(t)$. The initial condition $\tilde{p}_{A_{10}}(0) = \tilde{p}_0$ and $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = -C \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} + t)$ gives us $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \tilde{p}_0 \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} + t) = \tilde{p}_0 \cos(t)$ with $C = -\tilde{p}_0$. We have $\dot{x}(t) = \tilde{p}_0 \sin(t)$. We have

$$(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) = (\tilde{p}_0 \sin(t), \tilde{p}_0 \cos(t))$$

With $t_{A_2} = \pi + t_{A_1}$ will

$$\begin{aligned} & (\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))) = \\ & (\tilde{p}_0 \sin(t_{A_1}), \tilde{p}_0 \cos(t_{A_1})) = \\ & (\tilde{p}_0 \sin(\pi - t_{A_2}), \tilde{p}_0 \cos(\pi - t_{A_2})) = \\ & (\tilde{p}_0 \sin(t_{A_2}), -\tilde{p}_0 \cos(t_{A_2})) = \\ & (\dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}))) \end{aligned}$$

We have that $\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ and $\tilde{p}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = -\tilde{p}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ if $t_{A_1} = \pi - t_{A_2}$.

6.2. What we already know about situation B. For L_B we have the Euler-Lagrange curves following the Euler-Lagrange equations (2.3) that is $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}(t) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$. We see that $\ddot{p}(x(t)) =$

$$-\dot{x}(t) \implies \ddot{p}(x(t)) = -\ddot{x}(t)$$

and we have $\ddot{x}(t) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ this gives us:

$$(6.1) \quad \ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) = -\hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$$

For the existence and continuity of $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t))$ see section 6.4 below.

We start by studying the Euler-Lagrange curves $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ in the first quadrant of the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

We see that when the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ moves forward in t in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\dot{x}_1 = 0, \tilde{p}_1 = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$ will we have that $\tilde{p}_1 = \dot{\tilde{p}}_1 = -\dot{x}_1 = 0$ and $\ddot{x}_1 = \hat{p}_1 \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} = \tilde{p}_1 \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} > 0$. The Euler-Lagrange curve therefore moves in the \dot{x}_1 direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\dot{x}_1 = 0, \tilde{p}_1 = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$. The Euler-Lagrange curve will enter the interior of the first quadrant.

We know that in the first quadrant will \tilde{p} decrease and \dot{x} increase in t .

We see from (6.1): $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) = -\hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ and with $\hat{p}(x(t)) = \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ will we have $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) = -\tilde{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$. That gives us $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) < 0$ in the interior of the first quadrant. $\tilde{p}(x(t)) = \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ will be concave as a function of t in the interior of the first quadrant. This does not show us that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x})$ will be concave as a function of \dot{x} , this is also not needed here.

We have that at the point $(\dot{x}_1 = 0, \tilde{p}_1 = \tilde{p}_0)$ will \tilde{p} be concave and decreasing as a function of t . We also know that \dot{x} is increasing as a function of t .

We know that because \tilde{p} is decreasing and concave as function of t in the interior of the first quadrant and we start from $(\dot{x}_1 = 0, \tilde{p}_1 = \tilde{p}_0)$ with $\tilde{p}_1 = 0$ entering the interior of the first quadrant, will the Euler-Lagrange curve reach some point $(\dot{x}_1 = \dot{x}_c, 0)$ for $t = t_c$. See proposition 11 in the appendix. We know that a solution exists see the appendix 3.6.

This tells us that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{B_1} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

For situation A we know the exact solutions for the Euler-Lagrange equation. That imply that we know the solutions from some arbitrary point $(\dot{x}_1 = 0, \tilde{p}_1 = \tilde{p}_0)$ for $t = t_0$ to some point $(\dot{x}_1 = \dot{x}_d, 0)$ for $t = t_d$. We know that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{A_1} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))$$

We see from the two results above that:

(6.2)

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{B_1} \in R, t_{A_1} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

This is illustrated below.

We now repeat the arguments for following the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ backwards in t at $(\dot{x}_2 = 0, \tilde{p}_2 = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the \dot{x} direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

We start by studying the Euler-Lagrange curves $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ in the second quadrant of the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

We see that when the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ moves backward in t in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\dot{x}_2 = 0, \tilde{p}_2 = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ will we have that $\tilde{p}_2 = \hat{p}_2 = -\dot{x}_2 = 0$ and $\ddot{x}_2 = \hat{p}_2 \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} = \tilde{p}_2 \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} < 0$. The Euler-Lagrange curve therefore moves in the \dot{x} direction in the

(\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point (\dot{x}_2, \tilde{p}_2) backward in t . The Euler-Lagrange curve will enter the interior of the second quadrant.

We know that in the second quadrant will \tilde{p} and \dot{x} increase backward in t .

We see from (6.1): $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) = -\hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ and with $\hat{p}(x(t)) = \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ will we have $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) = -\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$. That gives us $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) > 0$ in the interior of second quadrant. $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ will be convex as a function of t in the interior of the second quadrant. This does not show us that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x})$ will be convex as a function of \dot{x} , this is also not needed here. That $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ is convex as a function of t in the interior of second quadrant shows us that $\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))$ is also convex backward in t as long as we are in the interior of second quadrant.

We have that at the point $(\dot{x}_2 = 0, \tilde{p}_2 = -\tilde{p}_0)$ will \tilde{p} be convex and increasing backward in t . We also know that \dot{x} is increasing backward in t .

We know that because \tilde{p} is increasing and convex backward in t in the interior of second quadrant and we start from $(\dot{x}_2 = 0, \tilde{p}_2 = -\tilde{p}_0)$ with $\tilde{p}_2 = 0$ and entering the interior of second quadrant will the Euler-Lagrange curve reach some point $(\dot{x}_2 = \dot{x}_e, 0)$ for $t = t_e$. **you can not in that place anticipate the same notations:** $\dot{x}_2 = \dot{x}_c = \dot{x}_2 = \dot{x}_c$ for $t = t_e$!!!!!! See proposition 11 in the appendix. We know that a solution exists see the appendix 3.6.

This tells us that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in] -\tilde{p}_0, 0[: \exists t_{B_2} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{B_2}(x_{B_2}(t_{B_2}))$$

For situation A we know the exact solutions for the Euler-Lagrange equation. That imply that we know the solutions from some arbitrary point $(\dot{x}_2 = 0, \tilde{p}_2 = \tilde{p}_0)$ for $t = t_0$ to some point $(\dot{x}_2 = \dot{x}_e, 0)$ for $t = t_e$. We know that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in] -\tilde{p}_0, 0[: \exists t_{A_2} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{A_2}(x_{A_2}(t_{A_2}))$$

We see from the two results above that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in] -\tilde{p}_0, 0[: \exists t_{B_2} \in R, t_{A_2} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{A_2}(x_{A_2}(t_{A_2})) = \hat{p}_{B_2}(x_{B_2}(t_{B_2}))$$

Analog arguments and results can be found following the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ backwards in t at $(\dot{x}_4 = 0, \tilde{p}_4 = \tilde{p}_0)$ and forwards in t at $(\dot{x}_3 = 0, \tilde{p}_3 = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the $-\dot{x}$ direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

6.3. The step by step reconstruction. Figure 6 illustrates, a step in situation A and B . It is explained further below.

FIGURE 6

We would like to assert that $\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ for each step, along Euler-Lagrange curves.

For situation A_1 we have (2.2): $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) \\ \hat{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \\ \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) \end{pmatrix}$. For situation B_1 we have (2.3): $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \\ \hat{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) \end{pmatrix}$

We remember (6.2) that:

$$\forall \tilde{p}_S \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{B_1} \in R, t_{A_1} \in R : \tilde{p}_S = \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

This tells us that

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \tilde{p}_{S_{to}} \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{B_1_{to}} \in R, t_{A_1_{to}} \in R : \\ \tilde{p}_{S_{to}} = \hat{p}_{A_1_{to}}(x_{A_1_{to}}(t_{A_1_{to}})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1_{to}}(t_{B_1_{to}})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \tilde{p}_{S_{from}} \in]0, \tilde{p}_0[: \exists t_{B_1_{from}} \in R, t_{A_1_{from}} \in R : \\ \tilde{p}_{S_{from}} = \hat{p}_{A_1_{from}}(x_{A_1_{from}}(t_{A_1_{from}})) = \\ \hat{p}_{B_1_{from}}(x_{B_1_{from}}(t_{B_1_{from}})) \end{aligned}$$

We introduce $\tilde{p}_{S_{to}} = \tilde{p}_{S_{from}} + \Delta \tilde{p}$, $t_{A_1_{to}} = t_{A_1_{from}} + \Delta t_{A_1}$, $t_{B_1_{to}} = t_{B_1_{from}} + \Delta t_{B_1}$.

We see that $0 < \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) < \dot{x}_{c_{A_1}}(t_{c_{A_1}})$ and $0 < \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) < \tilde{p}_0$, we use the Euler-Lagrange equation and see that $-\dot{x}_{c_{A_1}}(t_{c_{A_1}}) < \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) < 0$ and $0 < \ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) < \tilde{p}_0$.

We also see that $0 < \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) < \dot{x}_{c_{B_1}}(t_{c_{B_1}})$ and $0 < \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) < \tilde{p}_0$, we use the Euler-Lagrange equation and see that $-\dot{x}_{c_{B_1}}(t_{c_{B_1}}) < \tilde{\tilde{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) < 0$ and $0 < \ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) < \infty$.

That tells us that for $\Delta\tilde{p} < 0$ will $0 < \Delta t_{A_1} < \infty$ and $0 < \Delta t_{B_1} < \infty$. Later on we let $\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0$.

These limitations are used later on to ensure that expressions like $\frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}$ are well defined.

FIGURE 7

We know that if $from \rightarrow to$, that is $t_{A_1-from} \rightarrow t_{A_1-to}$ and $t_{B_1-from} \rightarrow t_{B_1-to}$, or $\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0$, then will the point $(\dot{x}_{A_1-from}, \tilde{p}_{A_1-from})$ follow an Euler-Lagrange curve to $(\dot{x}_{A_1-to}, \tilde{p}_{A_1-to})$ and the point $(\dot{x}_{B_1-from}, \tilde{p}_{B_1-from})$ will follow an Euler-Lagrange curve to $(\dot{x}_{B_1-to}, \tilde{p}_{B_1-to})$. Further more $\tilde{p}_{A_1-from} = \tilde{p}_{B_1-from}$ and $\tilde{p}_{A_1-to} = \tilde{p}_{B_1-to}$.

Requiring that $\tilde{p}_{A_1}(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ for each step, requires that $\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ for each step because $\tilde{p}_{A_1}(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))$ and $\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$. We define $\Delta\hat{p}_{A_1} = \hat{p}_{A_1-to} - \hat{p}_{A_1-from}$ and analog for $\Delta\hat{p}_{A_1}, \Delta\tilde{p}_{A_1}, \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_1}, \Delta\hat{p}_{B_1}$. This way we select a suitable $\Delta\hat{p}_{B_1}$ for every $\Delta\hat{p}_{A_1}$. That would give us $\Delta\hat{p} = \Delta\hat{p}_{A_1} = \Delta\hat{p}_{B_1} = \Delta\tilde{p} = \Delta\tilde{p}_{A_1} = \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_1}$, with $t_{A_1-to} = t_{A_1-from} + \Delta t_{A_1}$ and $t_{B_1-to} = t_{B_1-from} + \Delta t_{B_1}$. That requires that $\frac{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_1}}{\Delta\hat{p}_{B_1}} = 1$. We have for each Δt_{A_1} there exists Δt_{B_1} such that:

$$(6.3) \quad \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}}{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}} = \frac{\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) - \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = 1$$

We have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} &= \Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} \iff \\ \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) &= \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) - \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) &\iff \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) &= \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) + \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) &\iff \\ x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) &= \hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) + \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) &\iff \\ t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1} &= x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) \iff \\ \Delta t_{B_1} &= x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) - \\ t_{B_1} \end{aligned}$$

We know that $x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})$ is an increasing function of t_{B_1} and that $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ is a decreasing function of t_{B_1} in the first quadrant. We have that $x_B \in C^3(R)$ and $\hat{p}_{B_1} \in C^3(R)$. This ensures that x_{B_1} and \hat{p}_{B_1} have inverse continuous functions in the first quadrant.

We define $\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1}) = x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) - t_{B_1}$

This gives us

$$\Delta t_{B_1} = \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})$$

We know that $\hat{p}_{A_1} \in C^\infty(R)$ and $x_{A_1} \in C^\infty(R)$ this together with the continuity of x_B , \hat{p}_{B_1} , $\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}$ and $x_{B_1}^{-1}$ ensures that ψ is a continuous function in the first quadrant.

We study $\frac{\hat{p}_{A_1}}{\hat{p}_{B_1}}$ to get an equation we will use later. We note that $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \neq 0$ because according to (2.3) is $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = -\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})$. We know that $-\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) < 0$ in the first quadrant making $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) < 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have that } \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) &= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\Delta t_{A_1}} \text{ and } \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta t_{B_1}} &= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} &= \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\Delta t_{A_1}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta t_{B_1}}} = \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\Delta t_{A_1}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\Delta t_{A_1}}}{\frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \Delta t_{A_1}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))} \frac{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}} \text{ and having (6.3) } \frac{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\Delta \dot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = 1, \text{ that is al-} \\
&\text{ready assumed.}
\end{aligned}$$

For later use we have the equation:

$$(6.4) \quad \frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}}$$

Using the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory and knowing that $\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \neq 0$ because we are in the first quadrant. We have:

$$\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = \frac{-\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{-\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}$$

That is we have, using (6.4) that:

$$(6.5) \quad \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}}$$

We study $\frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}$ to get an equation we will use later. We note that $\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t) \neq 0$.

We have that $\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}}{\Delta t_{A_1}}$ and $\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}}{\Delta t_{B_1}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} &= \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\Delta t_{B_1}}} = \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}}}{\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \Delta t_{A_1}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})}{\Delta t_{A_1}} = \\
&\text{,using (6.5),} \\
&= \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{A_1})} =
\end{aligned}$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} =$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1}) - \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}$$

For later use we have the equation:

$$(6.6) \quad \frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1}) - \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}$$

We remember the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory (2.3): $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \\ \ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) \end{pmatrix}$ and (2.2):

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) \\ \ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \\ \hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) \end{pmatrix}.$$

We know that $\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \neq 0$ and that $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \neq 0$ and $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) \neq 0$.

We also remember that $\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$.

We can write:

$$\frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\hat{p}_{A_1}(x_{A_1}(t_{A_1}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))} = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

For later use we have the equation:

$$(6.7) \quad \frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

We have from our previous deduced equations (6.6) and (6.7):

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1}) - \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

We introduce the function, remembering that $\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_A) \neq 0$.

$$(6.8) \quad k(\dot{x}_A(t_A), \dot{x}_B(t_B)) = \frac{\dot{x}_B(t_B)}{\dot{x}_A(t_A)} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1}) - \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\ddot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \implies$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1} + \Delta t_{A_1}) - \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \psi(t_{B_1}, t_{A_1}, \Delta t_{A_1})) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) =$$

$k(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}), \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ Or

$$(6.9) \quad \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = k(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}), \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$$

We remember (6.3): $\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}}{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}} = 1$.

We now follow the Euler-Lagrange trajectory backwards at $(\dot{x} = 0, \hat{p} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ in the \dot{x} direction. Analog we obtain the equations.

$$(6.10) \quad \lim_{\Delta t_{A_2} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{A_2})} = k(\dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}), \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}))$$

with $\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_2}}{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}} = 1$.

We remember the start position are $(\dot{x}_{A_1} = 0, \hat{p}_{A_1} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$, $(\dot{x}_{A_2} = 0, \hat{p}_{A_2} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$ and $(\dot{x}_{B_1} = 0, \hat{p}_{B_1} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0)$, $(\dot{x}_{B_2} = 0, \hat{p}_{B_2} = -\tilde{p}_0 < 0)$. We have at start that $\hat{p}_{B_1} = \hat{p}_{A_1} = -\hat{p}_{A_2} = -\hat{p}_{B_2}$. As we continue to construct the new S lines will we along the Euler-Lagrange trajectories have that $\hat{p}_{B_1} = \hat{p}_{A_1} = -\hat{p}_{A_2} = -\hat{p}_{B_2}$. We also have that $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}$ and $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_2} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}$.

At start is $\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{A_1} = \dot{x}_{A_2} = \dot{x}_{B_2} = 0$.

We have that $\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ and $\tilde{p}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = -\tilde{p}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ as we have that $t_{A_1} = \pi - t_{A_2}$ see (proposition 5). We also have that $\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1} = \Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}$ and $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_2}$ as we have that $t_{A_1} = \pi - t_{A_2}$.

See figure 8.

FIGURE 8

We study equation (6.9).

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = k(\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}), \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})} = \frac{\dot{x}_B(t_B)}{\dot{x}_A(t_A)} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = 1$$

We study equation (6.10) and get

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} = 1$$

We combine these equations to

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} &= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \Leftrightarrow \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} - \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \right) &= \end{aligned}$$

0 \Leftrightarrow

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \left(\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2})) - \right. \\ \left. \Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \right) &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})} - \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \right) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

We know that $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}$ exist and that $\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})} =$

1, because $\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$ and $\dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) = \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})$.

We have that $\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})} - \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \right)$

and $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})}$ exist, this tells us that $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))}$

exist.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})} - \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \right) &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2}) \dot{x}_{A_2}(t_{A_2})} &= \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} \Leftrightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$(6.11) \quad \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{B_2}}(t_{B_2}))} = 1$$

We will now investigate what happens at $\dot{x}_{A_1_End} > \dot{x}_{A_1} = \dot{x}_{B_1} > 0$ and at $\dot{x}_{B_2_End} > \dot{x}_{A_2} = \dot{x}_{B_2} > 0$.

We have that $\tilde{\tilde{p}}_{A_1}(\dot{x}_{A_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant and having $\tilde{\tilde{p}}_{A_1}(0) = 0$ gives us $\tilde{\tilde{p}}_{A_1}(\dot{x}_{A_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant.

We let

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start.\epsilon} &= \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start} - \hat{\tilde{p}}_{\epsilon A_1} \\ \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon} &= \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End} + \hat{\tilde{p}}_{\epsilon A_1} \end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{\epsilon A_1} > 0$ and $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{\epsilon A_1}$ is small, and $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon} < \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start.\epsilon} < \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start} = \tilde{\tilde{p}}_0$ and $0 = \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End} < \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon} < \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start.\epsilon}$.

In situation A we will start having $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start.\epsilon}$. We would like to end having some $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon}$. We write $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon} - \hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_Start.\epsilon}$ as $\hat{\tilde{p}}_{A_1_End.\epsilon} -$

$\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = \Delta * \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon} = \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,1} + \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,2} + \dots + \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,n}$ by letting
 $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j} = \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}(t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j} + \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}) - \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}(t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j})$.

In situation A we will start having $t_{A_{1_start_}\epsilon}$. We have $t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j} = t_{A_{1_start_}\epsilon} + \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,i}$. We end having some $t_{A_{1_end_}\epsilon} = t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,n} = t_{A_{1_start_}\epsilon} + \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,i}$. We let $\Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,1} = \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,2} = \dots = \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,n} = \frac{t_{A_{1_end_}\epsilon} - t_{A_{1_start_}\epsilon}}{n}$.

We have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{t_{A_{1_end_}\epsilon} - t_{A_{1_start_}\epsilon}}{n} = 0$.

That is $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j} = 0$.

We have that $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j} = 0$.

6.3.1. *First we need to prove that $\dot{x}_{B_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$ for $\hat{p}_{B_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = -\hat{p}_{B_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$.* We know that $\dot{x}_{A_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = \dot{x}_{A_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$ and $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = -\hat{p}_{A_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$. We need to show that $\dot{x}_{B_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$ and that $\hat{p}_{B_{1_Start_}\epsilon} = -\hat{p}_{B_{2_Start_}\epsilon}$. This will be done in much the same way as showing that $\dot{x}_{B_{1_end}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_end}}$ for $\hat{p}_{B_{1_end}} = -\hat{p}_{B_{2_end}} = 0$, this is done below. We will continue this section after the next section on page 37.

6.3.2. *We will now prove $\dot{x}_{B_{1_end}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_end}}$.* We remember that $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} = \Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}$ and $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_2} = \Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}$. We have that $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}$. Giving us $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}$. Note that $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} < 0$.

We will now investigate what happens at $\dot{x}_{A_{1_End}} > \dot{x}_{A_1} = \dot{x}_{B_1} > 0$ and at $\dot{x}_{B_{2_End}} > \dot{x}_{A_2} = \dot{x}_{B_2} > 0$.

We have that $\ddot{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant and having $\ddot{p}_{B_1}(0) = 0$ gives us $\ddot{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant. We have

To this place I accept all (except for some notations and the form of editing) and I understand your considerations. But what follows below is not true. The expansion below - if it is w.r.t t then it can not be taken at the point \dot{x}_{B_1} moreover \hat{p}_{B_1} is only of C^2 and so on You have to change that

We will investigate what happens for n large and not for $n \rightarrow \infty$.

For n large will we have that $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} \simeq \Delta t_{B_1} \ddot{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$

That is we have

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} = \Delta t_{B_1} \ddot{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) + R(t_{B_1}, \Delta t_{B_1}) \iff$$

$$\Delta t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j} (\Delta \hat{p}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}) = \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}}{\ddot{p}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(\dot{x}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}))} - \frac{R(t_{B_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})}{\ddot{p}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(\dot{x}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}))} \iff$$

$$\Delta t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j} (\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}) = \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}}{\ddot{p}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(\dot{x}_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}(t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}))} + R_{\Delta t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}}(t_{B_{1_}\epsilon,j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1_}\epsilon,j}) \iff$$

$$\Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) = \check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})$$

For n large will we denote $\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}}{\check{\check{p}}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}))}$ as $\check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})$.

Note that for $n \rightarrow \infty$ will we have $\Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) = \check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})$.

We have that $\check{\check{p}}_{B_2}(\dot{x}_{B_2}) > 0$ in the interior of second quadrant and having $\check{\check{p}}_{B_2}(0) = 0$ gives us $\check{\check{p}}_{B_2}(\dot{x}_{B_2}) > 0$ in the interior of second quadrant.

We have that $\check{\check{p}}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant and having $\check{\check{p}}_{B_1}(0) = 0$ gives us $\check{\check{p}}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant.

We have analog for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}) = \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}{\check{\check{p}}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}))} + R_{\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\frac{-\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}}{\check{\check{p}}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}))} + R_{\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) \iff$$

$$\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) = \check{\Delta} t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})$$

We would like to introduce

We have for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) = \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}} + \Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}) \iff$$

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}})$$

\iff

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta x_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta x_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})$$

We define $R_{\Delta x_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}} + \Delta t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta} t_{B_{1-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}))$$

We have for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon j}}) = \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}} + \Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}) \iff$$

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta} t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}) \iff$$

$$\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta} t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta x_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$$

$$\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta x_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon j}})$$

We define $R_{\Delta x_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon j}}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon j}}) =$

$$\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta}t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})) - \dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}} + \check{\Delta}t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{2,\epsilon j}}))$$

We also have for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}) = \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}) =$$

0.

$$\lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})} = \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{2,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{2,\epsilon j}})} = 0.$$

$$\lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} = \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{2,\epsilon j}})}{\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}})} = 0.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) &= \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + \Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) \iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) &= \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + \check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}) \iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) &= \check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}) \iff \\ \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &= \frac{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} \iff \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &= \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}) + R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &\iff \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &= \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \left(1 + \frac{R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}\right) &\iff \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &= \\ 1 + \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R_{\Delta\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}, \Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &\iff \\ \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} &= 1 + 0 = 1 \iff \end{aligned}$$

$$(6.12) \quad \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}})} = 1$$

We have analog

$$(6.13) \quad \lim_{\Delta\hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}})}{\check{\Delta}\dot{x}_{B_{2,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{2,\epsilon j}})} = 1$$

Remembering equation (6.11) that is

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}))} = 1$$

We have for $\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0$ that $\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})$ and $\Delta \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) = \check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2})$.

$$\text{This gives us that } \lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}))} = 1$$

Using $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} = \Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}$ and $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}$ we have

$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$: $\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) \simeq \check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))$ for sufficiently large n .

We have for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) + R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j}) = \check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})).$$

$$\text{We remember equation (6.12)} \quad \lim_{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})}{\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})} = 1$$

$$\text{and equation (6.13)} \quad \lim_{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{2-\epsilon}j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j+1}) - \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})}{\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})} = 1.$$

This tells us that for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ can we:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n (\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) - R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j})) =$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))$$

Having $n \rightarrow \infty$ we can use $\check{\Delta} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j} = \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}$.

This gives us

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n (\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) - R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j})) =$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})) \iff$$

$$\frac{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n (\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) - R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j}))}{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))} =$$

1 \iff

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j})) - R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))} =$$

1

We have $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$: $\lim_{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j} \rightarrow 0} R(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon}j}) = 0$.

We have that for all $j \in 1, 2, \dots, n$ that

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1-\epsilon}j}))}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))} = 1 \iff$$

This requires that the terms exist.

We will investigate the term

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))}.$$

We select $\max\left(\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))}\right)$ for $j = 1$ to n .

We will call this maximum

$$\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})_{\max}}{(\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})))_{\max}}.$$

Note that this is just something we call

$\max\left(\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))}\right)$. It doesn't mean that we take the maximum of both numerator and denominator separately.

We select $\min\left(\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))}\right)$ for $j = 1$ to n . We will call this minimum

$$\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})_{\min}}{(\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j})))_{\min}}.$$

Note that this is just something we call

$\min\left(\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon},j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon}j}))}\right)$. It doesn't mean that we take the minimum of both numerator and denominator separately.

PROPOSITION 6. *We have that for $n \in R^+$ will $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$. We denote $\frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$ as $\max(\frac{a_j}{b_j})$, where $a_j \in R_+$, $b_j \in R_+$, $j \leq n$, $j \in N$ and $n \in N$.*

REMARK 5. $\frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$ doesn't mean that we take maximum of both numerator and denominator separately.

REMARK 6. Note that $\frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$ is a function of n .

REMARK 7. When using this proposition would we like to avoid $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \leq \infty$. This is a reason for introducing $\hat{p}_{A_{1-End,\epsilon}}$.

For $n = 1$ will $\frac{a_1}{b_1} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$ because $\frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} = \max(\frac{a_j}{b_j})$.

For $n = 2$ will we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_1}{b_1} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \iff \\ a_1 b_{n-j \max} &\leq b_1 a_{n-j \max} \iff \\ a_1 b_{n-j \max} - b_1 a_{n-j \max} &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{a_2}{b_2} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \iff$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_2 b_{n-j \max} &\leq b_2 a_{n-j \max} \iff \\ b_2 a_{n-j \max} - a_2 b_{n-j \max} &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

This gives us

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 b_{n-j \max} - b_1 a_{n-j \max} &\leq b_2 a_{n-j \max} - a_2 b_{n-j \max} \iff \\ a_1 b_{n-j \max} + a_2 b_{n-j \max} &\leq b_1 a_{n-j \max} + b_2 a_{n-j \max} \iff \\ b_{n-j \max} (a_1 + a_2) &\leq a_{n-j \max} (b_1 + b_2) \iff \\ \frac{a_1 + a_2}{b_1 + b_2} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 3$ will, if we assume that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3}{b_1 + b_2 + b_3} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \iff \\ \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + a_3}{(b_1 + b_2) + b_3} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}, \text{ we have that } \frac{a_1 + a_2}{b_1 + b_2} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \text{ and } \frac{a_3}{b_3} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \end{aligned}$$

we can define $\tilde{a}_1 = a_1 + a_2$, $\tilde{b}_1 = b_1 + b_2$, $\tilde{a}_2 = a_3$ and $\tilde{b}_2 = b_3$

This gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + a_3}{(b_1 + b_2) + b_3} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \iff \\ \frac{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{a}_2}{\tilde{b}_1 + \tilde{b}_2} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}, \text{ we know this to be true. We have that} \\ \frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3}{b_1 + b_2 + b_3} &\leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}} \end{aligned}$$

We can continue this for all $n = j$. We get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$$

□

PROPOSITION 7. We have that for $n \in R^+$ will $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$. We denote $\min(\frac{a_j}{b_j})$ as $\frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$, where $a_j \in R_+$, $b_j \in R_+$, $j \leq n$, $j \in N$ and $n \in N$.

REMARK 8. $\frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$ dosen't mean that we take minimum of both numerator and denominator separately.

REMARK 9. Note that $\frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$ is a function of n .

REMARK 10. When using this proposition would we like to avoid $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \geq -\infty$. This is a reason for introducing $\hat{p}_{A_1 \text{ End } \epsilon}$.

For $n = 1$ will $\frac{a_1}{b_1} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$ because $\frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} = \min(\frac{a_j}{b_j})$.

For $n = 2$ will we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_1}{b_1} &\geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} \iff \\ a_1 b_{n-j \min} &\geq b_1 a_{n-j \min} \iff \\ a_1 b_{n-j \min} - b_1 a_{n-j \min} &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_2}{b_2} &\geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} \iff \\ a_2 b_{n-j \min} &\geq b_2 a_{n-j \min} \iff \end{aligned}$$

$$b_2 a_{n-j \min} - a_2 b_{n-j \min} \leq 0$$

This gives us

$$a_1 b_{n-j \min} - b_1 a_{n-j \min} \geq b_2 a_{n-j \min} - a_2 b_{n-j \min} \iff$$

$$a_1 b_{n-j \min} + a_2 b_{n-j \min} \geq b_1 a_{n-j \min} + b_2 a_{n-j \min} \iff$$

$$b_{n-j \min} (a_1 + a_2) \geq a_{n-j \min} (b_1 + b_2) \iff$$

$$\frac{a_1 + a_2}{b_1 + b_2} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$$

For $n = 3$ will, if we assume that

$$\frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3}{b_1 + b_2 + b_3} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} \iff$$

$$\frac{(a_1 + a_2) + a_3}{(b_1 + b_2) + b_3} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}, \text{ we have that } \frac{a_1 + a_2}{b_1 + b_2} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} \text{ and } \frac{a_3}{b_3} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$$

we can define $\tilde{a}_1 = a_1 + a_2$, $\tilde{b}_1 = b_1 + b_2$, $\tilde{a}_2 = a_3$ and $\tilde{b}_2 = b_3$

This gives us

$$\frac{(a_1 + a_2) + a_3}{(b_1 + b_2) + b_3} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}} \iff$$

$$\frac{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{a}_2}{\tilde{b}_1 + \tilde{b}_2} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}, \text{ we know this to be true. We have that}$$

$$\frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3}{b_1 + b_2 + b_3} \geq \frac{a_{n-j \max}}{b_{n-j \max}}$$

We can continue this for all $n = j$. We get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \leq \frac{a_{n-j \min}}{b_{n-j \min}}$$

□

We use proposition 6 to prove that:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}))} \leq$$

$$\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}})_{\max}}{(\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}})))_{\max}}$$

We remember that

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \lim_{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}))} =$$

0.

$$\text{This tells us that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}})_{\max}}{(\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}})))_{\max}} =$$

0.

We use proposition 7 to prove that:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}))} \geq$$

$$\frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}})_{\min}}{(\Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1-\epsilon^j}}) \dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}}(t_{B_{2-\epsilon^j}})))_{\min}}$$

$$\text{We remember that } \lim_{\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1})}{\Delta \dot{x}_{A_1}(t_{A_1}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}) \frac{1}{k(\dot{x}_{A_1}, \dot{x}_{B_{1-\epsilon^j}})}} = 0.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}))} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}, \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{1.\epsilon}j}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}, -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\epsilon}j}) \dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}(t_{B_{2.\epsilon}j}))} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \frac{\int_{\dot{x}_{B_{1.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\dot{x}_{B_{2.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) d\dot{x}_{B_1}}{\int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{End}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2})) d\dot{x}_{B_2}} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \frac{\int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p}}{\int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p}} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \lim_{\hat{p}_{\epsilon A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p}}{\int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p}} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \lim_{\hat{p}_{\epsilon A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{End}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \lim_{\hat{p}_{\epsilon A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{End}.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p} \Leftrightarrow \\
& \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{End}}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{End}}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2.\text{Start}}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p} \Leftrightarrow \\
& \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0 \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \int_0^{-\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p} \Leftrightarrow \\
& \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0 \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0 \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p} \Leftrightarrow
\end{aligned}$$

$$(6.14) \quad \int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} = \int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$$

We see that

if $\dot{x}_{B_{1.\text{end}}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2.\text{end}}}$ will $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_2})$ and equation (6.14) will be fulfilled.

If $\dot{x}_{B_{1.\text{end}}} > \dot{x}_{B_{2.\text{end}}}$ will $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) > \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_2})$ and we therefor have $\int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} > \int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$. Equation (6.14) will not be fulfilled.

If $\dot{x}_{B_{1.\text{end}}} < \dot{x}_{B_{2.\text{end}}}$ will $\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_1}) < \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_{B_2})$ and we therefor have $\int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}} < \int_{\frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}_{B_{1.\text{Start}}}^0} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}$. Equation (6.14) will not be fulfilled.

This tells us that

$$\dot{x}_{B_{1.\text{end}}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2.\text{end}}}$$

6.3.3. *Continuing of First we need to get from $\hat{p}_{A_{1.\text{Start}}}$ to $\hat{p}_{A_{1.\text{Start}.\epsilon}}$.* This discussion is a continuation of the discussion on page 28.

In situation A we start having $t_{B_{1.\text{start}}} = 0$. We have $t_{B_{1.\alpha}j} = t_{B_{1.\text{start}.\epsilon}} + \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}j}$. We end having some $t_{B_{1.\text{start}.\epsilon}} = t_{B_{1.\alpha}n} =$

$t_{B_{1_start}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.j}$. We let $\Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.1} = \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.2} = \dots = \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.n} = \frac{t_{B_{1_start.\epsilon}} - t_{B_{1_start}}}{n}$

We have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{t_{B_{1_start.\epsilon}} - t_{B_{1_start}}}{n} = 0$.

That is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.2} = \dots = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta t_{B_{1.\alpha}.n} = 0$.

In situation A we start having $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start}} = 0$. We would like to end having some $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start.\epsilon}}$. We write $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start.\epsilon}} - \hat{p}_{A_{1_Start}}$ as $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start.\epsilon}} - \hat{p}_{A_{1_Start}} = \Delta * \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}} = \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.1} + \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.2} + \dots + \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.n}$ by letting $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.j} = \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.j}(t_{A_{1.\alpha}.j} + \Delta t_{A_{1.\alpha}.j}) - \hat{p}_{A_{1.\alpha}.j}(t_{A_{1.\alpha}.j})$

We remember that $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} = \Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}$ and $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_2} = \Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}$. We have that $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2}$. Giving us $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_2} = -\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}$. Note that $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1} < 0$. This tells us that $\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start.\epsilon}} = -\tilde{p}_{B_{2_Start.\epsilon}}$.

At $\hat{p}_{A_{1_Start}} = 0$ will we use $\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1} \simeq \frac{(\Delta t_{B_1})^2}{2!} \ddot{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$.

Analog to the above section we get

$$\lim_{\hat{p}_{\alpha A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start.\epsilon}}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \lim_{\hat{p}_{\alpha A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{2_Start.\epsilon}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{2_Start}}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p} \iff$$

$$\lim_{\hat{p}_{\alpha A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start}}^{\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start.\epsilon}}}} \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \partial \tilde{p} = \lim_{\hat{p}_{\alpha A_1} \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start.\epsilon}}^{-\tilde{p}_{B_{1_Start}}}} \dot{x}_{B_2}(t_{B_2}) \partial \tilde{p}$$

Analog to the above section we get

$$\dot{x}_{B_{1_Start.\epsilon}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_Start.\epsilon}}$$

6.3.4. *What $\dot{x}_{B_{1_end}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_end}}$ gives us.* We will define \dot{x}_{B_End} to be $\dot{x}_{B_End} = \dot{x}_{B_{1_End}} = \dot{x}_{B_{2_End}}$.

This tell us that the two curves 1 and 2 are going to have $\hat{p}_{B_1} = \hat{p}_{B_2} = 0$ for some $\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{B_2} = \dot{x}_{B_End}$, we see the curves meet at $(\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{B_2} = \dot{x}_{B_End}, 0)$.

At the point $(\dot{x}_B = \dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{B_2} = \dot{x}_{B_End} > 0, \tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_1} = \tilde{p}_{B_2} = 0)$ will we using (2.3): $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}(t) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(x(t))) \end{pmatrix}$ have that $\ddot{x}_B(t) = 0$ and $\ddot{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t)) = -\dot{x}_B(t) < 0$. We have that at the point $(\dot{x}_B = \dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{B_2} > 0, \tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_1} = \tilde{p}_{B_2} = 0)$ in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system will the curve move vertical in the $-\tilde{p}$ direction thereby entering the second quadrant.

Following the Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0)$ and $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the $-\dot{x}$ direction can be done analog. We get, analog, that both curves are going to intersect the \dot{x} axes when $\tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_3} = \tilde{p}_{B_4} = 0$ and $\dot{x}_B = \dot{x}_{B_3} = \dot{x}_{B_4} < 0$ and at the point $(\dot{x}_B = \dot{x}_{B_3} = \dot{x}_{B_4} < 0, \tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_3} = \tilde{p}_{B_4} = 0)$, analog we have that at the

($\dot{x}_B = \dot{x}_{B_3} = \dot{x}_{B_4} < 0, \tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_3} = \tilde{p}_{B_4} = 0$) will the curve enter the fourth quadrant.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curves in all four quadrants are connected. We remember that the start points where chosen arbitrarily. We have that at some point ($\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0$) will we following an Euler-Lagrange curve come back to the point ($\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0 > 0$) after some time t_p . We have that $\dot{x}(a) = \dot{x}(a + t_p)$ and $\tilde{p}(a) = \tilde{p}(a + t_p)$ for $a \in R$ and some $t_p > 0$. We have that $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(t)) = (\dot{x}, \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x))$ with parameter t is an orbit and as we have seen (proposition 2) that $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t is therefor periodic.

That prove to us that the Euler-Lagrange condition (2.3): $(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t))}{\partial \dot{x}_B(t)}) = (\frac{-\dot{x}_B(t)}{\tilde{p}_B(x(t)) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))})$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve, has periodic solutions.

□

6.4. Differentiability of \tilde{p}, \hat{p} and \dot{x}_B . We will compare the degree of differentiability of expressions to each other. We will use the function Ω to get the degree of differentiability of an expression. Like $g \in C^3(R)$ having $\Omega(g) \geq 3$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) \\ (6.15) \quad \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}^2(t) \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}^2}(\dot{x}(t)) \\ \ddot{\tilde{p}}(\dot{x}(t)) &= \ddot{\ddot{x}}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}(t)) + 3\ddot{x}(t) \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}^2}(\dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}^3(t) \frac{\partial^3 \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}^3}(\dot{x}(t)) \end{aligned}$$

We also have

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) &= \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) &= \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) + \dot{x}^2(t) \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{p}}{\partial x^2}(x(t)) \\ (6.16) \quad \ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) &= \ddot{\ddot{x}}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) + 3\dot{x}(t) \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial^2 \hat{p}}{\partial x^2}(x(t)) + \dot{x}^3(t) \frac{\partial^3 \hat{p}}{\partial x^3}(x(t)) \end{aligned}$$

We would like $\Omega(\ddot{\tilde{p}}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B))) \geq 0$ partly because we would like $\ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t))$ to exist and be continues. That requires because of (6.16) that $\Omega(\ddot{\ddot{x}}_B(t_B)) \geq 0$ or $\Omega(x_B(t_B)) \geq 3$ and $\Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_B}{\partial x_B}(x_B(t))) \geq 2$.

This give us $\Omega(\hat{p}_B(x_B(t_B))) \geq 3$ or $\Omega(\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x(t))) \geq 3$ or $\Omega(h(x(t))) \geq 4$.

We would also like $\Omega(\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B))) \geq 0$ because we would like $\tilde{p}(x(t))$ to exist and be continues.

That requires because of (6.15) that $\Omega(\ddot{x}_B(t_B)) \geq 0$ or $\Omega(x_B(t_B)) \geq 3$ and $\Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_B}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_B)) \geq 1$

This give us $\Omega(\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B))) \geq 2$ and with $\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x})$ will we have $\Omega(g) \geq 3$.

We remember the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory (2.3): $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \\ \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial p}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) \end{pmatrix}$.

$\hat{p}_B(x(t)) = \dot{x}_B(t)$ giving us $\Omega(\hat{p}_B(x(t))) = \Omega(\dot{x}_B(t))$ or

$$(6.17) \quad \Omega(\hat{p}_B(x(t))) = \Omega(x_B(t))$$

We see that we need $\Omega(\hat{p}_B(x(t))) = \Omega(\dot{x}_B(t)) \geq 3$ and that is what we have.

We have that $\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial p}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))$. Because of (6.17) will we have $\Omega(\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = \Omega(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial p}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) \iff$

$\Omega(\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = \Omega(\frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}) = \Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))$. This fits with $\Omega(x_B(t_B)) \geq 3$ and $\Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_B}{\partial \dot{x}_B}(\dot{x}_B)) \geq 1$.

We might have that $x_B \in C^3(R)$, $\dot{x}_B \in C^2(R)$, $g_B \in C^3(R)$, $\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B)) \in C^2(R)$, $\ddot{p}_B(x_B(t_B)) \in C^1(R)$, $\hat{p}_B(x(t)) \in C^3(R)$ and $h_B \in C^4(R)$.

Having $\hat{p}(x) = \frac{\partial h_B}{\partial x}(x) = \frac{\partial h_A}{\partial x}(x) = -\frac{1}{2}x^2$ gives us $\Omega(\hat{p}(x)) = \infty$ and $\Omega(h(x)) = \infty$.

We have that $x_B \in C^3(R)$, $\dot{x}_B \in C^2(R)$, $g_B \in C^3(R)$, $\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B)) \in C^2(R)$, $\ddot{p}_B(\dot{x}_B(t_B)) \in C^\infty(R)$, $\hat{p}_B(x(t)) \in C^\infty(R)$ and $h_B \in C^\infty(R)$.

7. Situation B is tied to situation C for each step

We intend in this section to prove that the periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange curves with some period length T_B in a situation B imply the periodicity with period length T_C of the Euler-Lagrange curves in a situation C . The proof uses a geometric step by step reconstruction of the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation B to the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation C .

We follow the Euler-Lagrange curve for situation C . First we follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ forward in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and backward in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \tilde{p} direction.

We want to tie the situation B to C for each step. In situation B we also follow the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ forward in t starting at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and backward in t starting at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \tilde{p} direction.

Later on we repeat the arguments for following the Euler-Lagrange curve backward in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and forward in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the $-\tilde{p}$ direction.

The illustration below illustrates how we follow the Euler-Lagrange curve backward and forward in t in our $B - C$ step by step reconstruction. The red arrow illustrates us following the Euler-Lagrange curve backward and the black arrow illustrates us following the Euler-Lagrange curve forward.

Again we will denote variables with indexes according to there belonging quadrant number 1,2,3 or 4. The index 0 denotes our start point.

7.1. What we already know about situation C . For L_C we have Euler-Lagrange curves following the Euler-Lagrange equations (0.5 from chapter 3) written as $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$. We see that

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t))) \implies$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t))) + \hat{p} \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial t}(\tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t))) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t))) \implies$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \hat{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$$

We start by studying the Euler-Lagrange curves $(\hat{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$ in the forth quadrant of the (\hat{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

The Euler-Lagrange curve $(\hat{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$ follows forward in t in the (\hat{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\hat{x} = \hat{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \tilde{p} direction. At this point will we have $\dot{\tilde{p}} = \hat{x}_{4.0} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} > 0$ and $\ddot{x} = \hat{p} \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}} = 0$. The Euler-Lagrange curve therefore moves in the \tilde{p} direction in the (\hat{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\hat{x}_{4.0}, \tilde{p}_{4.0})$. The Euler-Lagrange curve will enter the interior of the forth quadrant.

We know that in the forth quadrant will \tilde{p} and \hat{x} increase in t .

We see from $\ddot{x}(t) = \hat{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$ with $\frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}} > 0$, $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x} < 0$ and $\hat{x} < 0$ giving $\ddot{x}(t) > 0$ in the interior of the forth quadrant. $\hat{x}(t)$ will be convex as a function of t in the interior of the forth quadrant.

For the differentiability of \hat{x}_C see 7.3 below.

This does not show us that $\hat{x}(t)$ will be convex as a function of \tilde{p} , this is also not needed here.

We have that at the point $(\hat{x} = \hat{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ will \hat{x} be convex and increasing as a function of t . We also know that \tilde{p} is increasing as a function of t .

We know that because \hat{x} is increasing and convex as a function of t in interior of forth quadrant and we start from $(\hat{x} = \hat{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ with $\ddot{x} = 0$ entering the interior of forth quadrant, will the Euler-Lagrange curve reach some point $(0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_k > 0)$ for $t = t_k$, see proposition 11.

We know that a solution exists see the appendix 3.6.

This tells us that:

$$\forall \hat{x}_S \in]\hat{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_C \in R : \hat{x}_S = \hat{x}_C(t_C)$$

For situation B we know the constructed solutions for the Euler-Lagrange equation. That imply that we know the solutions from some arbitrary point $(\hat{x} = \hat{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ for $t = t_0$ to some point $(0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_k > 0)$ for $t = t_k$. We know that:

$$\forall \hat{x}_S \in]\hat{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_B \in R : \hat{x}_S = \hat{x}_B(t_B)$$

We see from the two results above that:

$$(7.1) \quad \forall \hat{x}_S \in]\hat{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_C \in R, t_B \in R : \hat{x}_S = \hat{x}_B(t_B) = \hat{x}_C(t_C)$$

This is illustrated below.

We now repeat the arguments for following the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ backwards in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \dot{x} direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

We start by studying the Euler-Lagrange curves $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ in the first quadrant of the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

We see that the direction of the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ moves backward in t in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system at the point $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$. At this point we will have that $\ddot{\tilde{p}} = \dot{x}_{1.0} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} < 0$ and $\ddot{x} = \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} = 0$. The Euler-Lagrange curve therefore moves in the \tilde{p} direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system. The Euler-Lagrange curve will enter the interior of the first quadrant.

We know that in the first quadrant will \tilde{p} decrease and \dot{x} increase in t . That is \tilde{p} will increase and \dot{x} will decrease in backward in t .

We see from $\ddot{x}(t) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(\dot{x}(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} > 0$, $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} < 0$ and $\dot{x} > 0$ giving $\ddot{x}(t) < 0$ in the interior of first quadrant. $\dot{x}(t)$ will be concave as a function of t in the interior of the first quadrant. This does not show us that $\dot{x}(t)$ will be concave as a function of \tilde{p} , this is also not needed here. That $\dot{x}(t)$ is concave as a function of t shows us that $\dot{x}(t)$ is concave as a function of backward in t .

We have that at the point $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ will \dot{x} be concave and decreasing backward in t . We also know that \tilde{p} is increasing backward in t .

We know that because \dot{x} is decreasing and concave backward in the interior of the first quadrant and we start from $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$

with $\ddot{x} = 0$ entering in the interior of the first quadrant, will the Euler-Lagrange curve reach some point $(0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_m > 0)$ for $t = t_m$. See proposition 11 in the appendix. We know that a solution exists see the appendix 3.6.

This tells us that:

$$\forall \dot{x}_S \in]0, \dot{x}_0[: \exists t_C \in R : \dot{x}_S = \dot{x}_C(t_C)$$

For situation B we know the constructed solutions for the Euler-Lagrange equation. That imply that we know the solutions from some arbitrary point $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ for $t = t_0$ to some point $(0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_m > 0)$ for $t = t_m$. We know that:

$$\forall \dot{x}_S \in]0, \dot{x}_0[: \exists t_B \in R : \dot{x}_S = \dot{x}_B(t_B)$$

We see from the two results above that:

$$\forall \dot{x}_S \in]0, \dot{x}_0[: \exists t_C \in R, t_B \in R : \dot{x}_S = \dot{x}_B(t_B) = \dot{x}_C(t_C)$$

Analog arguments and results can be found following the Euler-Lagrange curve $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(\dot{x}(t)))$ backwards in t at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0} < 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and forwards at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0} > 0, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in t in the $-\dot{x}$ direction in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system.

7.2. The step by step reconstruction. Figure 9 illustrates, using non analytical notation, a step in situation B and C . It is explained further below.

We would like to assert that $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$ and $\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})$ for each step.

$$\text{For situation } B_4 \text{ we have (2.3): } \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \\ \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \\ \dot{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))) \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$\text{For situation } C_4 \text{ we have (0.5): } \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \\ \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \\ \dot{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))) \end{pmatrix}.$$

We remember (7.1):

$$\forall \dot{x}_S \in]\dot{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_{C_4} \in R, t_{B_4} \in R : \dot{x}_S = \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$$

This tells us that

$$\forall \dot{x}_{S_{to}} \in]\dot{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_{C_{4,to}} \in R, t_{B_{4,to}} \in R : \\ \dot{x}_{S_{to}} = \dot{x}_{B_{4,to}}(t_{B_{4,to}}) = \dot{x}_{C_{4,to}}(t_{C_{4,to}})$$

$$\forall \dot{x}_{S_{from}} \in]\dot{x}_0, 0[: \exists t_{C_{4,from}} \in R, t_{B_{4,from}} \in R : \\ \dot{x}_{S_{from}} = \dot{x}_{B_{4,from}}(t_{B_{4,from}}) = \dot{x}_{C_{4,from}}(t_{C_{4,from}})$$

We introduce $\dot{x}_{S_{from}} = \dot{x}_{S_{to}} + \Delta \dot{x}$, $t_{B_{4,to}} = t_{B_{from}} + \Delta t_B$, $t_{C_{4,to}} = t_{C_{4,from}} + \Delta t_{C_4}$.

FIGURE 9

We see that $\dot{x}_0 < \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) < 0$ and $0 < \tilde{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) < \tilde{p}_{cC_4}(x_{cC_4}(t_{cC_4}))$, we use the Euler-Lagrange equation and see that $0 < \tilde{\hat{p}}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}), \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) = \dot{x}(t_{C_4}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t_{C_4})) < \infty$ and $0 < \ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) = \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))) < \infty$

That tells us that for $\Delta \dot{x} > 0$ will $0 < \Delta t_{C_4} < \infty$. Later on we let $\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0$.

These limitations are used later on to ensure that expressions like $\frac{\dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})}$ are well defined.

We know that if $from \rightarrow to$, that is $t_{B_4-from} \rightarrow t_{B_4-to}$ and $t_{C_4-from} \rightarrow t_{C_4-to}$, or $\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0$, then will the point $(\tilde{p}_{B_4-from}, \dot{x}_{B_4-from})$ follow an Euler-Lagrange curve to $(\tilde{p}_{B_4-to}, \dot{x}_{B_4-to})$ and the point $(\tilde{p}_{C_4-from}, \dot{x}_{C_4-from})$ will follow an Euler-Lagrange curve to $(\tilde{p}_{C_4-to}, \dot{x}_{C_4-to})$. Further more $\dot{x}_{B_4-from} = \dot{x}_{C_4-from}$ and $\dot{x}_{B_4-to} = \dot{x}_{C_4-to}$.

FIGURE 10

Requiring that $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$ for each step with $t_{B_4} = t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}$ and $t_{C_4} = t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}$, we must have that $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_4}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_4}} = 1$. We have

$$(7.2) \quad \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_4}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_4}} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}{\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \dot{x}_{C_4} = \Delta \dot{x}_{B_4} &\iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) &\iff \\ \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) = \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) + \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) &\iff \\ t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) + \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) &\iff \\ \Delta t_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) + \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) - t_{C_4} \end{aligned}$$

We know that \dot{x}_{C_4} is an increasing function of t_{C_4} in the fourth quadrant and that $\dot{x}_{C_4} \in C^2(\mathbb{R})$. This ensures that \dot{x}_{C_4} has an inverse continuous function in the fourth quadrant.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We define } \omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4}) = \\ \dot{x}_{C_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) + \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) - t_{C_4} \end{aligned}$$

This gives us

$$\Delta t_{C_4} = \omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})$$

We know that $\dot{x}_{B_4} \in C^2(R)$ and from section 7.3 below that $\dot{x}_{C_4} \in C^2(R)$ this together with the continuity of $\dot{x}_{C_4}^{-1}$ ensures that ω_4 is an continuous function in the forth quadrant.

We also have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \dot{x}_{C_4} &= \Delta \dot{x}_{B_4} \iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) &= \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) &= \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \iff \\ t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4} &= \dot{x}_{B_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \iff \\ \Delta t_{B_4} &= \dot{x}_{B_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) - t_{B_4} \end{aligned}$$

We know that \dot{x}_{B_4} is an increasing function of t_{B_4} in the forth quadrant and that $\dot{x}_{B_4} \in C^2(R)$. This ensures that \dot{x}_{B_4} has an inverse continuous function in the forth quadrant.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We define } \Xi_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{C_4}) &= \\ \dot{x}_{B_4}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) - t_{B_4} & \\ \text{This gives us} & \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta t_{B_4} = \Xi_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})$$

We know that $\dot{x}_{B_4} \in C^2(R)$ and from section 7.3 below that $\dot{x}_{C_4} \in C^2(R)$ this together with the continuity of $\dot{x}_{B_4}^{-1}$ ensures that Ξ_4 is an continuous function in the forth quadrant.

We also require that $\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})$ for each step with $t_{B_1} = t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}$ and $t_{C_1} = t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1}$, we must have that $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_1}} = 1$. We have

$$(7.3) \quad \frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_1}} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1}) - \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})} = 1$$

This equation is also illustrated on figure 10.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \dot{x}_{C_1} &= \Delta \dot{x}_{B_1} \iff \\ \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) &= \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1}) - \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1}) \iff \\ \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1}) &= \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) + \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1}) \iff \\ t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1} &= \dot{x}_{C_1}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) + \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \iff \\ \Delta t_{C_1} &= \dot{x}_{C_1}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) + \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) - t_{C_1} \end{aligned}$$

We know that \dot{x}_{C_1} is an decreasing function of t_{C_1} in the first quadrant and from section 7.3 below that $\dot{x}_{C_1} \in C^2(R)$. This ensures that \dot{x}_{C_1} has an inverse continuous function in the first quadrant.

$$\text{We define } \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1}) = \dot{x}_{C_1}^{-1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) + \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) - t_{C_1}$$

This gives us

$$\Delta t_{C_1} = \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})$$

We know that $\dot{x}_{B_1} \in C^2(R)$ and from section 7.3 below that $\dot{x}_{C_1} \in C^2(R)$ this together with the continuity of $\dot{x}_{C_1}^{-1}$ ensures that ω_1 is an continuous function in the first quadrant.

The requirement $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$ and $\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}) = \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})$ also gives us knowing that $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \neq 0$ and $\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \neq 0$:

$$(7.4) \quad \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \frac{\dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})}$$

Requiring that $\tilde{p}_{B_4}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) = \tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ for each step, requires that $\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ for each step because $\tilde{p}_{B_4}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) = \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))$ and $\tilde{p}_{B_1}(\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$. We have

$$(7.5) \quad \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = 1$$

We define $\Delta\hat{p}_{B_1} = \hat{p}_{B_1-to} - \hat{p}_{B_1-from}$ and analog for $\Delta\tilde{p}_{B_1}, \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_4}, \Delta\hat{p}_{B_4}$. That would give us $\Delta\hat{p} = \Delta\hat{p}_{B_1} = \Delta\hat{p}_{B_4} = \Delta\tilde{p} = \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_1} = \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_4}$ with $t_{B_4} = t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}$ and $t_{B_1} = t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}$. That requires that $\frac{\Delta\hat{p}_{B_1}}{\Delta\tilde{p}_{B_4}} = 1$. We have

$$(7.6) \quad \frac{\Delta\hat{p}_{B_1}}{\Delta\tilde{p}_{B_4}} = \frac{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) - \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\tilde{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \tilde{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} = 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\hat{p}_{B_4} = \Delta\tilde{p}_{B_1} &\iff \\ \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) &= \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) - \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) &\iff \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1})) &= \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) + \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) &\iff \\ x_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) &= \hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) + \\ \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))) &\iff \\ t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1} &= x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) \iff \\ \Delta t_{B_1} &= x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) - \\ t_{B_1} \end{aligned}$$

We know that $x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})$ is a increasing function of t_{B_1} that $\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))$ is a decreasing function of t_{B_1} in the first quadrant. We have that $x_B \in C^3(R)$ and $\hat{p}_{B_1} \in C^3(R)$. This ensures that x_{B_1} and \hat{p}_{B_1} have inverse continuous functions in the first quadrant.

We define

$$\phi(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4}) = x_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}(\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4})) - \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))) + \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})))) - t_{B_1}$$

This gives us

$$\Delta t_{B_1} = \phi(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})$$

We know that $\hat{p}_{B_4} \in C^\infty(R)$ and $x_{B_4} \in C^3(R)$ this together with the continuity of x_{B_1} , \hat{p}_{B_1} , $\hat{p}_{B_1}^{-1}$ and $x_{B_1}^{-1}$ ensures that ϕ is an continuous function in the first quadrant.

We remember that $\Delta t_{B_1} = \phi(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})$, $\Delta t_{B_4} = \Xi_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})$ and $\Delta t_{C_1} = \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})$

We have in the first quadrant.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t_{C_1} &= \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1}) = \\ &= \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \phi(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})) = \\ &= \omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \phi(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Xi_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{C_4}))) = \\ &= \phi_C(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{C_4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta t_{C_1} = \phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})$$

We study $\frac{\ddot{x}_{C_4}}{\ddot{x}_{B_4}}$ to get an equation we will use later. We note that $\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \neq 0$.

We have that $\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) = \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{C_4})}{\Delta t_{C_4}}$ and $\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}}$.

$$\frac{\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})}{\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{C_4})}{\Delta t_{C_4}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}}} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{C_4})}{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}}{\frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}}} =$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{C_4})}{\Delta \dot{x}(t_{B_4})} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})} =$$

$\lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$ and having (7.2) $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_1}} = 1$, that is already

assumed.

For later use we have the equation:

$$(7.7) \quad \frac{\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})}{\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$$

We study $\frac{\ddot{p}_{C_4}}{\ddot{p}_{C_1}}$ to get an equation we will use later. We note that $\ddot{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \neq 0$.

We have that $\ddot{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) = \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\Delta t_{C_4}}$ and $\ddot{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) =$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{C_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \dot{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\Delta t_{C_1}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))} &= \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\Delta t_{C_4}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{C_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\Delta t_{C_1}}} = \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\Delta t_{C_4}}}{\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})}{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \Delta t_{C_4}} = \\
&= \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4})) - \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1} + \phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})) - \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})))} \frac{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})}{\Delta t_{C_4}}
\end{aligned}$$

For later use we have the equation:

$$(7.8) \quad \frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))} = \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})}{\Delta \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \Delta t_{C_4}}$$

Analog to this we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} &= \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta t_{B_1}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\Delta t_{B_4}}} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}}{\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\Delta t_{B_4}}} = \\
&= \frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \Delta t_{B_4}}{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}.
\end{aligned}$$

We know from (7.6) that $\frac{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\Delta \hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} = 1$. We have

$$(7.9) \quad \frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$$

We have from the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory that:

$\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) = -\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})$ and $\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) = -\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})$ and we know that

$\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \neq 0$ and that $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) \neq 0$. We can write

$$\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}), \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}), \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} = \frac{-\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{-\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}$$

Using (7.9): $\frac{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\ddot{\hat{p}}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$ we get:

$$(7.10) \quad \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$$

We have $\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) > 0 \neq 0$, $\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) > 0 \neq 0$ and $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))) > 0 \neq 0$. We have the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory and We know that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_{B_4}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))) = \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})))$ because $\tilde{p}_{B_4}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) = \tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))$ because $\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4}) = \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$. We see:

$$\frac{\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}{\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial p}(\tilde{p}_{B_4}(\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial p}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})))} = \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))}$$

Using (7.7) we get:

$$(7.11) \quad \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} = \frac{\ddot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}{\ddot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}}$$

We have analog that

$$(7.12) \quad \frac{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))}{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))} = \frac{\ddot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\ddot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})}{\Delta t_{B_1}}$$

We see

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}}}{\lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})}{\Delta t_{B_1}}} &= \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \iff \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega_4(t_{B_4}, t_{C_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}} \lim_{\Delta t_{B_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_1}}{\omega_1(t_{B_1}, t_{C_1}, \Delta t_{B_1})} &= \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} \iff \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{C_4}}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})} \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}{\Delta t_{B_4}} &= \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \iff \\ \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{C_4}}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})} &= \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4})) \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1})) \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Using (7.5): } \frac{\hat{p}_{B_4}(x_{B_4}(t_{B_4}))}{\hat{p}_{B_1}(x_{B_1}(t_{B_1}))} = 1 \text{ and (7.10): } \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} = \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{C_4}}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})} &= \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \lim_{\Delta t_{B_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{B_4}}{\phi_B(t_{B_1}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{B_4})} = \\ \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})} & \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$(7.13) \quad \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{C_4}}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})} = \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}$$

$$\lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta t_{C_4}}{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4})} = \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} \iff$$

$$1 = \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi_C(t_{C_1}, t_{B_1}, t_{C_4}, t_{B_4}, \Delta t_{C_4}) \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\Delta t_{C_4} \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} \iff$$

$$1 = \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))} \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} \iff$$

$$1 = \lim_{\Delta t_{C_4} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) \Delta x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})}$$

This gives us

$\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))\Delta x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}) \simeq \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})$ for sufficiently small Δt_{C_4} .

For sufficiently small Δt_{C_4} will we have that $\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))\Delta x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}) = \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + R(\Delta x_{C_1})$. Where R is some rest function.

We have that $\lim_{\Delta x_{C_4,j} \rightarrow 0} R(\Delta x_{C_1}) = 0$.

We have that

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \lim_{\Delta x_{C_4,j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}))\Delta x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = \\ &\lim_{\Delta x_{C_4,j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) + R(\Delta x_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = \\ 1 &+ \lim_{\Delta x_{C_4,j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} \Leftrightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\lim_{\Delta x_{C_4,j} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_1})}{\hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))\Delta x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = 0$$

We remember (7.2) $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_4}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_4}} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4} + \Delta t_{B_4}) - \dot{x}_{B_4}(t_{B_4})}{\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4} + \Delta t_{C_4}) - \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4})} = 1$

and (7.3) $\frac{\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1}}{\Delta \dot{x}_{C_1}} = \frac{\dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1} + \Delta t_{B_1}) - \dot{x}_{B_1}(t_{B_1})}{\dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1} + \Delta t_{C_1}) - \dot{x}_{C_1}(t_{C_1})} = 1$.

That is $\Delta \dot{x}_{B_4} = \Delta \dot{x}_{C_4}$ and $\Delta \dot{x}_{B_1} = \Delta \dot{x}_{C_1}$.

We use the equation for $\Delta \hat{p}_{A_1}$ on page 30.

We use the equation on page 29.

We get $\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \dot{x}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}), \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} = \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{1,\epsilon j}}), \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}$ and analog we get

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta \dot{x}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}), \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}} = \Delta \dot{x}_{B_{4,\epsilon j}}(t_{B_{4,\epsilon j}}), \Delta \hat{p}_{A_{1,\epsilon j}}.$$

We can get

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} \simeq \dot{x}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} \Delta t_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} \text{ for large } n.$$

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}} \simeq \dot{x}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}} \Delta t_{C_{4,\epsilon j}} \text{ for large } n.$$

We will summarize the terms in the equations

$$\forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \hat{p}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}))\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}) = \hat{p}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}))\Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}) + R(\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}), \text{ giving us for } n \text{ large.}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} + R(\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}})) =$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}} \implies$$

$$\frac{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} - R(\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}))}{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}} = 1 \implies$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} - R(\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}} = 1.$$

We know that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}} - R(\Delta x_{C_{1,\epsilon j}}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}})\Delta x_{C_{4,\epsilon j}}}$ exist.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}} - R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}))}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} =$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \right)$$

We would like to investigate term $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}$.

We select $\max\left(\frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}\right)$ for $j = 1$ to n and call the selected

terms $\frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\max}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\max}}$

We select $\min\left(\frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}\right)$ for $j = 1$ to n and call the selected

terms $\frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\min}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\min}}$

will

$$\frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\min}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\min}} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \leq \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\max}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\max}}.$$

See proposition (6) and (7).

We have that

$$\text{However we know from } \forall j \in 1, 2, \dots, n : \lim_{\Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}} \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(t_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})} =$$

0 that

$$\text{also } \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\max}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\max}} = 0 \text{ and } \frac{R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})_{\min}}{(\hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}})_{\min}} = 0.$$

We have $0 \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \leq 0$ giving us:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} = 0$$

and we know that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}$ exist.

Remember that we have seen that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \right)$ exist and that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}$ exist.

We have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \right) +$

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} =$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \right) =$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}. \text{ We see that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}}$$

exist.

We have that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \right) = \\
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n R(\Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \iff \\
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} - 0
\end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} = 1 \\
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} = 1 \iff \\
& 1 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{1.\epsilon j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \hat{p}_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}(x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}) \Delta x_{C_{4.\epsilon j}}} \iff \\
& 1 = \lim_{\hat{p}_{\epsilon A_1} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{x_{1_Start.\epsilon}}^{x_{1_End.\epsilon}} \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}) dx}{\int_{x_{4_Start.\epsilon}}^{x_{4_End.\epsilon}} \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}) dx} \iff \\
& 1 = \frac{\int_0^{x_1} \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}) dx}{\int_0^{x_4} \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}) dx} \iff \\
& \int_0^{x_1} \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}) dx = \int_0^{x_4} \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}) dx \iff
\end{aligned}$$

$$(7.14) \quad \int_0^{x_1} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx = \int_0^{x_4} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx$$

If $x_1 = x_4$ will (7.14) be fulfilled.

If $x_1 > x_4$ will $\int_0^{x_1} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx < \int_0^{x_4} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx$ because $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$ and (7.14) will not be fulfilled.

If $x_1 < x_4$ will $\int_0^{x_1} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx > \int_0^{x_4} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}) dx$ because $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$ and (7.14) will not be fulfilled.

We have that (7.14) imply: $x_1 = x_4$. We have

$$x_{C_1}(t_{C_1}) = x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \text{ and } \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))$$

$$\text{We have } \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \iff \hat{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) = \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \iff$$

$$\tilde{p}_{C_1}(x_{C_1}(t_{C_1})) = \tilde{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))$$

For $\tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} = 0$ have we the situation from which we started our transformation. These points don't change after the start under the transformation.

We remember the start position are $(\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p}_{B_4} = 0)$, $(\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{1.0} > 0, \tilde{p}_{B_1} = 0)$ and $(\dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{4.0} < 0, \tilde{p}_{C_4} = 0)$, $(\dot{x}_{C_1} = \dot{x}_{1.0} >$

$0, \tilde{p}_{C_1} = 0$). We have at start that $\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4}$ and $\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{C_1}$. As we continue to construct the new S lines will we along the Euler-Lagrange trajectories have that $\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4}$ and $\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{C_1}$.

We have derived above that:

$\tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1}$ as we continue to construct the new S lines.

We know that the Euler-Lagrange trajectory in situation B are going to intersect the \tilde{p} axes at $(\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{B_4} = 0, \tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_4} = \hat{p}_{B_1})$. When $\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = 0$ will the Euler-Lagrange trajectory in situation C because of $\tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1}$ intersect the \tilde{p} axes at $(\dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = 0, \tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1})$. We see the curves meet at $(\dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = 0, \tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} > 0)$.

At the point $(\dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = 0, \tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} > 0)$ will we using (0.5): $\left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \\ \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \\ \hat{p}_{C_4}(x_{C_4}(t_{C_4})) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_{C_4}(\dot{x}_{C_4}(t_{C_4}))) \end{array} \right)$ that $\tilde{p}_C(x_C(t_{C_4})) = \tilde{p}_C(x_C(t_C)) = 0$ and $\ddot{x}_C(t_C) = \tilde{p}_C(x_C(t_C)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t_C))) > 0$. We have that at the point $(\dot{x}_{C_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4} = 0, \tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} > 0)$ in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) coordinate system will the curve move horizontal in the \dot{x} direction thereby entering the first quadrant.

Following the Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x}_{B_3} = \dot{x}_{3.0} < 0, \tilde{p}_{B_3} = 0)$ and $(\dot{x}_{B_2} = \dot{x}_{2.0} > 0, \hat{p}_{B_2} = 0)$ in the $-\tilde{p}$ direction can be done analog. We get analog that the curves in the third and second quadrant meet at $(\dot{x}_{C_3} = \dot{x}_{C_3} = 0, \tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_3} = \tilde{p}_{C_3} < 0)$ and that the curve there will move into the third quadrant.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curves in all four quadrants are connected. We have that $\dot{x}(a) = \dot{x}(a+t_p)$ and $\tilde{p}(a) = \tilde{p}(a+t_p)$ for $a \in R$ and some $t_p > 0$. We remember that the start points where chosen arbitrarily. We have that $(\dot{x}(t), \tilde{p}(t)) = (\dot{x}, \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x))$ with parameter t is an orbit and as we have seen (proposition 2) that $(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ with parameter t is therefor periodic.

That prove to us that the Euler-Lagrange condition $\left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{p}_C(x_C(t)) \\ \dot{x}_C(t) \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x}_C(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x_C(t)) \\ \hat{p}_C(x_C(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t))) \end{array} \right)$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve has periodic solutions.

□

7.3. Differentiability of \dot{x}_C , \tilde{p}_C and \hat{p}_C . We will compare the degree of differentiability of expressions to each other. We will use the function Ω to get the degree of differentiability of an expression. Like $g \in C^3(R)$ having $\Omega(g) = 3$.

We know from situation B that $\Omega(g) \geq 3$ and $\Omega(\frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_B(\dot{x}_B))) = \Omega(\frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C))) \geq 1$. or

$$\Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_B(t))) = \Omega(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}(\dot{x}_C(t))) \geq 1$$

We would like $\ddot{x}_C(t_C)$ to exist and be continues, for that we need $\Omega(\ddot{x}_C(t_C)) \geq 0$ that will give us $\Omega(x_C(t_C)) \geq 3$.

$\Omega(\ddot{x}_C(t_C)) \geq 0$ would according to (6.16) work with $\Omega(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_C}{\partial x_C}(x_C)) \geq 2$ and $\Omega(\hat{p}_C(x_C(t_C))) \geq 3$.

We remember the Euler-Lagrange equations along an Euler-Lagrange trajectory (0.5): $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{p}_C(x_C(t)) \\ \ddot{x}_C(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}_C(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x_C(t)) \\ \hat{p}_C(x_C(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t))) \end{pmatrix}$.

We have that $\ddot{p}_C(x_C(t)) = \dot{x}_C(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x_C(t))$ and we have that

$$\Omega(\ddot{p}_C(x_C(t_C))) \geq 2 \text{ and } \Omega(\dot{x}_C(t_C)) \geq 2 \text{ and } \Omega(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_C}{\partial x_C}(x_C(t))) \geq 2.$$

This work outs fine.

$\ddot{x}_C(t) = \hat{p}_C(x_C(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t)))$ and we have that

$$\Omega(\ddot{x}_C(t)) \geq 1 \text{ and } \Omega(\hat{p}_C(x_C(t))) \geq 3 \text{ and } \Omega(\frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t)))) \geq 1.$$

This work outs fine.

We have that $x_C \in C^3(R)$, $\ddot{x}_C \in C^0(R)$, $g_C = g_B \in C^3(R)$, $\tilde{p}_C(\dot{x}_C(t_C)) \in C^2(R)$, $\tilde{\tilde{p}}_C(\dot{x}_C(t_B)) \in C^0(R)$, $\hat{p}_C(x(t)) \in C^3(R)$ and $h_C \in C^4(R)$.

CHAPTER 5

Proof that the Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic

We intend in this chapter to proof that every Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic for some variable T under some conditions. We further more give an geometrical interpretation of the proof.

1. Rewriting the Euler-Lagrange equation

PROPOSITION 8. *Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^2$. let L be strictly convex w.r.t \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} > 0$, let L be strictly concave w.r.t x and let L be non separated w.r.t. x and \dot{x} in the set V then is $\left(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \right) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ an Euler-Lagrange equations in the set V along an Euler-Lagrange curve.*

That L is non separated w.r.t. x and \dot{x} is different from the constrains on L we have previously introduced. Under this constrain will we have that $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x}$ is not 0 everywhere in the set V

We remember that along an Euler-Lagrange curve will we have $\frac{d}{dt}(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) = \dot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$.

We have defined \tilde{p} and $\dot{\tilde{p}}$ as functions of x and \dot{x} . Along an Euler-Lagrange curve in V will:

$$(1.1) \quad \frac{d\tilde{p}}{dt}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \frac{d\dot{x}(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$(1.2) \quad \frac{d\dot{\tilde{p}}}{dt}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \frac{\partial x(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \frac{\partial \dot{x}(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

We can write these equations as:

$$(1.3) \quad \dot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$(1.4) \quad \ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} \ddot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{array} \right) = dt \left(\begin{array}{c} x(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) \\ (\hat{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) \end{array} \right)$$

□

We remember that the Euler-Lagrange equations rely on $\frac{d}{dt}(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) = \dot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ to apply along an Euler-Lagrange curve.

1.0.1. *Geometrical considerations.* We have the Euler-Lagrange condition: $\left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ \ddot{x} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ (\hat{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{array} \right)$. As introduced in the previous section.

We have seen that for $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ becomes the Euler-Lagrange condition $\left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{\tilde{p}}(x(t)) \\ \ddot{x}(t) \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ (\hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(\tilde{p}(x(t)))) \end{array} \right)$ this is equation (0.5).

Now we wish to prove the same theorem as proofed in chapter 5, but with L separated with respect to x and \dot{x} condition removed.

The Euler-Lagrange condition $\left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ \ddot{x} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ (\hat{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{array} \right)$ can be written as:

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{\tilde{p}} \\ \ddot{x} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} + \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ (\hat{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ \hat{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ -\dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{array} \right)$$

We will show how this equation fits together on figure 10 below

We can also see how values of the original vertical and horizontal $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$ isoline and $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ isoline are scaled. We have that $\frac{-dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{-dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}} = \frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$,

and $\frac{\partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{dt \dot{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}} = \frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$. The scale factor is $1 - \frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$

$$\frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$$

2. The Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system

PROPOSITION 9. Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^2$. let L be strictly convex w.r.t \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} > 0$, let L be strictly concave w.r.t x and let L be non separated w.r.t. x and \dot{x} in the set V then is $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})$ = $dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \int(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}} \right)$ an Euler-Lagrange equations in the set V along an Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system.

We scale the $\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}$ axis with the factor $\frac{1}{(1 - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}})} = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) &= dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right) \iff \\ \left(\frac{\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) &= dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

That works. See illustration below

We have

$$\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) = \partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \partial x \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{dt}$$

We assume that $\partial x \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{dt} = 0$, $\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{dt}$ is in general not 0. However the contribution of $\partial x \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{dt}$ becomes 0 when summarized.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\frac{\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system on a small scale has the same direction as the Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system, the length of a small vector is just changed with a factor of $\frac{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}}$. We can change the size of dt by multiplying it with a finite factor and not change the solution. This tells us that in the $(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})$ coordinate system will both of the following equations be Euler-Lagrange curves:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right) \text{ and } \left(\frac{\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right).$$

2. THE EULER-LAGRANGE CURVE IN THE $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ COORDINATE SYSTEM 13

We have that $(\frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}} \right)$ is an Euler-Lagrange

curves in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system. \square

THEOREM 3. *Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^3$, let L be strictly convex in the \dot{x} direction and let L be strictly concave in the x direction. Then will every Euler-Lagrange curve be periodic.*

We have that $(\frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}} \right)$ is an Euler-Lagrange

curves in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system. We see that the solution has the same form as $(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}{\tilde{p} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}} \right)$ in the (\tilde{p}, \dot{x}) coordinate system and is therefor always periodic. \square

Part 2

Appendix

CHAPTER 6

The set V and U

1. Growth condition 1 and 2

We remember that $L \in C^3(R \times R)$, and that we have the following assumptions on L

- (1) L is autonomous w.r.t to t .
- (2) L is separable w.r.t x and \dot{x} . We have $L = h(x) + g(\dot{x})$.
- (3) $\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} > 0$.
- (4) $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial x} < 0$.
- (5) L satisfy growth condition 3 as stated in proposition 11.

We will now study some growth condition on L and see how it effects V .

1.0.1. *Growth condition 1.* The following growth condition on L will ensure that V is some subset of the the set $R_{x\dot{x}}$:

Growth condition 1.

$$(1.1) \quad L(\dot{x}) \longrightarrow \infty \text{ for } \dot{x} \longrightarrow u$$

and/or

$$L(x) \longrightarrow -\infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow l$$

The growth condition tells us that there exists a u for which $L(\dot{x}) \longrightarrow \infty$ for $\dot{x} \longrightarrow u$ and/or there exists a l where $L(x) \rightarrow -\infty$ for $x \rightarrow l$.

Figure 1 is an illustration of some L that fulfill the growth condition.

1.0.2. *Growth condition 2.* We will now investigate how the set V in belonging to the set $R_{x\dot{x}}$ map over to the set U belonging to the set $R_{x\dot{p}}$. It is seen that for every point in V there is also a point in U , because the mapping $(\dot{x}, \dot{p}) = (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}(x, \dot{x})) = (\dot{x}, \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(x, \dot{x}))$ for L strictly concave w.r.t x is an one to one mapping.

We know that the strictly concavity w.r.t. x of L implies $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} < 0$ almost everywhere.

FIGURE 1

If we have $\frac{\partial L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow u$ for $x \rightarrow \infty \Leftrightarrow$
 $L(x) + c_1 \rightarrow \int u dx = ux + c_2$ for $x \rightarrow \infty \Leftrightarrow$

$$\frac{L(x)}{x} \rightarrow u + \frac{c}{x} = u \text{ for } x \rightarrow \infty$$

analog for $\frac{\partial L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow v$ for $x \rightarrow -\infty \Leftrightarrow$

$$\frac{L(x)}{x} \rightarrow u + \frac{c}{x} = v \text{ for } x \rightarrow \infty$$

If we let $u \rightarrow \infty$ and $v \rightarrow \infty$ then we get

$$\frac{L(x)}{\frac{\partial L(x)}{\partial x}} \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow \infty \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\frac{L(x)}{x} \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow \infty$$

and

$$\frac{L(x)}{\frac{\partial L(x)}{\partial x}} \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow -\infty \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\frac{L(x)}{x} \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow -\infty$$

that is we get $\frac{L(x)}{|x|} \rightarrow \infty$ for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$.

If we like to have $\frac{\partial L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow \infty$ for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$ then we need the following growth condition.

Growth condition 2.

$$(1.2) \quad \frac{L(x)}{|x|} \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow \pm\infty$$

This growth condition is illustrated below.

FIGURE 2

The function illustrated in figure 2 satisfy the growth condition. The function illustrated in figure 3 does not.

FIGURE 3

1.1. We assume that growth condition 1 w.r.t x and \dot{x} is fulfilled. If growth condition 1 is satisfied w.r.t. x and \dot{x} then V will be limited w.r.t. x and \dot{x} , in addition the growth condition 2 will be satisfied w.r.t. x and/or \dot{x} inside V . This is illustrated on figure 4 w.r.t. x and \dot{x} , the black border illustrates the limitation.

We have that L is separable w.r.t x and \dot{x} . That is we have $L(x, \dot{x}) = L_1(x) + L_2(\dot{x})$.

If L does not satisfy the growth condition 2 w.r.t x then $\frac{L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow$ some c for $x \rightarrow \pm \infty$ for all \dot{x} .

FIGURE 4

U would be a vertical strip in the $R_{\dot{x}, \tilde{p}}$ set. The convex area U is illustrated on figure 5.

FIGURE 5

1.2. We assume that growth condition 1 w.r.t x and \dot{x} is not fulfilled. We remember that L can be expressed as $L(x, \dot{x}) = L_x(x) + L_{\dot{x}}(\dot{x})$ and it is strictly convex w.r.t. \dot{x} and strictly concave w.r.t x .

If growth condition 1 w.r.t x and \dot{x} is not fulfilled will V be the set $R_{x\dot{x}}$ because there would exist no u and l from $L(\dot{x}) \rightarrow \infty$ for $\dot{x} \rightarrow u$ and $L(x) \rightarrow -\infty$ for $x \rightarrow l$ to limit the range of L .

If growth condition 2 w.r.t x is not fulfilled then will the mapping to U have the shape of a horizontal stripe in the $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}$ set, because it would be limited in the \tilde{p} direction to $\frac{L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow \tilde{p}_1$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$ and $\frac{L(x)}{\partial x} \rightarrow \tilde{p}_2$ for $x \rightarrow -\infty$. This U is illustrated on figure 6.

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

If growth condition 2 w.r.t. x is fulfilled then will the mapping to U be the $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}$ set. This U is illustrated on figure 7.

1.3. We assume that growth condition 1 w.r.t x is not fulfilled and it is w.r.t \dot{x} . If growth condition 1 w.r.t. \dot{x} is fulfilled, but it is not w.r.t. x , will U be like in section 1.2, except it will be limited w.r.t \dot{x} . U is illustrated on figure 8 and figure 9.

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

1.4. We assume that growth condition 1 w.r.t \dot{x} is not fulfilled and it is w.r.t x . If growth condition 1 w.r.t x is fulfilled, but it is not w.r.t \dot{x} , will growth condition 2 w.r.t. x be fulfilled and U would be the $R_{\dot{x}\tilde{p}}$ set. The convex area U is illustrated on figure 10.

FIGURE 10

2. $f'(x) = 0$ for strictly convex functions

Both the two functions illustrated on figure 11 and 12 are strictly convex functions.

The strictly convex function illustrated on figure 11 does not have any x with $f'(x) = 0$. The strictly convex function illustrated on figure 12 does have an x with $f'(x) = 0$.

From [4, Jean Mawhin - Michel Willem "Critical Point Theory and Hamiltonian Systems", p17] we have the following proposition:

FIGURE 11

FIGURE 12

PROPOSITION 10. Let $G \in C^1(\mathbb{R}^N, \mathbb{R})$ be a strictly convex function. The following properties are equivalent:

- a) There exists $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ such that $\nabla G(\bar{x}) = 0$.
- b) $G(x) \rightarrow \infty$ when $|x| \rightarrow \infty$.

We translate and renotate this proposition to the proposition below:

PROPOSITION 11. Let $f \in C^1(\mathbb{R})$ be a strictly convex function. The following properties are equivalent:

- a) There exists $\dot{x} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $f'(\dot{x}) = 0$.
- b) $f(x) \rightarrow \infty$ when $|x| \rightarrow \infty$.

If we have $f'(x) \rightarrow u$ for $x \rightarrow -\infty$ and $u < 0$ then will $f(x) \rightarrow -\infty$ for $x \rightarrow -\infty$ this is the function illustrated on figure 11.

We want to investigate L with strictly convexity w.r.t. \dot{x} and strictly concavity w.r.t. x that have $f'(\dot{x}) = 0$ as illustrated on figure 12. According to proposition 11 we need the growth condition $f(x) \rightarrow \infty$ when $|x| \rightarrow \infty$ to assure that.

The growth assumptions for L are:

Growth condition 3.

$$(2.1) \quad L(\dot{x}) \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow \pm\infty$$

$$(2.2) \quad L(x) \rightarrow -\infty \text{ for } x \rightarrow \pm\infty$$

3. Solutions of a system of m first-order equations.

From [5, p 93] we have:

”Remark: In Corollary 3 (below) and in what follows x is a point of a phase space of any (finite) dimension m . This corollary ”3” is called an Existence and Uniqueness theorem for solutions of a system of m first-order equations.”

3.1. Existence and Uniqueness theorem. From [5, p 93] we have:

”**Corollary 3.** A solution of the differential equation $\dot{x} = \mathbf{v}(x)$ with initial condition (t_0, x_0) in the domain of smoothness of the right-hand side exist and is unique (in the sense that any two solutions with a common initial condition coincide in some neighborhood of the point t_0).”

We look at $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{p}(x(t)) \\ \hat{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$.

We first look at $\hat{p}(x(t)) = -\dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))$, that is $\dot{x}(t) = -\frac{\hat{p}(x(t))}{\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))}$,

for $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \neq 0$. The equation is of the type $\dot{x} = v(x)$.

We now look at $\hat{x}(t) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve.

We have the Euler-Lagrange equations $\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t)) = \hat{p}(x(t))$ to apply along an Euler-Lagrange curve.

We have $\hat{x}(t) = \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t))) = \hat{p}(\dot{x}(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$ this is of the type $\hat{x} = v(\hat{x})$.

For initial condition (t_0, x_0, \dot{x}_0) with smooth $-\frac{\hat{p}(x(t))}{\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t))}$ and $\hat{p}(\dot{x}(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t)))$

will the solutions to $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{p}(x(t)) \\ \hat{x}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \hat{x}}{\partial \hat{p}}(\hat{p}(\hat{x}(t))) \end{pmatrix}$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve, exist and be unique.

3.2. Continuous and Differentiable dependence of the solutions on the initial condition. From [5, p 93] we have:

”**Corollary 4.** The solution of an equation ” $\dot{x} = \mathbf{v}(t, x)$ ” with smooth right-hand side depends smoothly on the initial assumptions.”

We see that two curves with two initial assumptions that are sufficiently close together will after any finite t be arbitrary close together.

3.3. Continuous and Differentiable dependence on a parameter. From [5, p 93] we have for $\dot{x} = \mathbf{v}(t, x; \alpha)$ where α is ranging over some domain A of the space R^a .

”**Corollary 6.** The value of the solution with initial condition $\varphi(t_0) = x_0$ at an instant t depends smoothly on the initial condition, the time, and the parameter α .”

3.4. Extension theorem. From [5, p 102] we have:

”**Corollary 9.** A solutions of the autonomous equations $\dot{x} = \mathbf{v}(x)$ with initial value in any compact set of the phase space can be continued forward (resp. backward) either infinitely or to the boundary of the compact set.”

A compact subset of a Euclidean space are the closed and bounded sets.

3.5. Locally rectifiable of $(\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) \rightarrow (-\dot{x}, \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}})$. From [5, p 103] we have:

”**Corollary 10.** Every smooth vector field is locally rectifiable in a neighborhood of each nonsingular point (a point where the vector field is nonzero)”. The vector field for our equation is $(\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) \rightarrow (-\dot{x}, \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}})$.

From [5, p 104] we have:

”**Corollary 11.** Any two smooth vector fields in domains of the same dimension can be transformed into each other by diffeomorphisms in sufficiently small neighborhoods of any nonsingular points.”.

We have situation A , B and C . The construction of B from A and of C from B is locally a diffeomorphisms as described above.

3.6. Existence and Uniqueness of $(\tilde{p}(x(t)), \dot{x}(t)) = (\tilde{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}(x(t)), \dot{x}(t))$.

From [5, p 107] we have:

”A differential equation of order n is an equation

$$(1) \quad \frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = F(t; x, \frac{dx}{dt}, \dots, \frac{d^{(n-1)}x}{dt^{(n-1)}})$$

Corollary. Let $u = (u_0; u_1, \dots, u_n)$ be a point of the domain U in which the right-hand side of Eq. (1) is defined. The solution φ of Eq. (1) with initial condition

$$\varphi(u_0) = u_1, \dot{\varphi}(u_0) = u_2, \dots, \varphi^{(n-1)}(u_0) = u_n$$

exists and is unique (in the sense that any two solutions with the same initial condition coincide on the intersection of their intervals of definition.)”

The Euler-Lagrange equation $\frac{d}{dt}(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x}(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t))) = 0$ is an second order ordinary differential equations, that can be expressed as a system of two first order ordinary differential equations.

From the corollary above do we see that the solution $x(t)$ exists and is unique. That is an Euler-Lagrange function exists and is unique.

Under some assumptions on L is $\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{\hat{p}}(x(t)) \\ \dot{\hat{x}}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial x}(x(t)) \\ \hat{p}(x(t)) \frac{\partial \dot{\hat{x}}}{\partial p}(\hat{p}(x(t))) \end{pmatrix}$, along an Euler-Lagrange curve, also unique. assumptions are 1-5

3.7. Closed phase curves. Our phase space would be (\dot{x}, \dot{p}) .

From [5, p 118] we have:

”**Corollary.** Through each point of the phase space of an autonomous system there passes one and only one phase curve.”

From [5, p 119] we have:

”**Theorem.** A maximal phase curve of an autonomous system either has no self-intersections or reduces to a single point, or is a closed phase curve (diffeomorphic to a circle).”

We would like to show, in our main theorem, that the Euler-Lagrange equation under our condition on L , follows a closed phase curve.

An example of an maximal phase curve of an autonomous system that has no self-intersections, is not a single point and is not a closed phase curve, is a spiral and is illustrated below.

CHAPTER 7

A proof sketch with Non-standard analysis

1. The use of non standard analysis differentials for geometrical argumentations.

As Non-standard analysis is not yet part of the commonly accepted mathematics will we only sketch a proof of our main theorem by use of Non-standard analysis.

The author believe that Non-standard analysis, in some form, should and will be the future of analysis.

A nonzero number ϵ is defined as infinitely small or infinitesimal, in nonstandard analysis, if $|\epsilon| < \frac{1}{n}$ for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. In R there is no nonzero infinitesimal. In nonstandard analysis a hyperreal structure $*R$ is defined to also contain infinitessimals.

In the example above one line of argumentation tells us that if ϵ exist and is a nonzero number then a number n_0 should be findable that would be $|\epsilon| > \frac{1}{n_0}$ that being not the case there can not exist a nonzero ϵ . I think this line of argumentation is wrong because if n_0 did exist then ϵ would not have to be infinitesimal small. An infinitely small ϵ would be smaller than any $\frac{1}{n_0}$.

Non-standard analysis can be seen as an attempt to bring argumentations with infinitessimals back into modern analysis.

The use of Non-standard analysis will be limited to the use of differentials like $\partial\tilde{p}$, $d\tilde{x}$ and $d\tilde{t}$. Geometrical argumentations with Non-standard analysis differentials will be central to the intended argumentation.

We will use d instead of ∂ if we want to emphasize that we are moving along some curve.

2. A proof sketch of our main theorem

We intend in this chapter to sketch a proof that every Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic for some variable T under some assumptions. We furthermore give an geometrical interpretation of the sketch.

THEOREM 4. *Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \longrightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^3$, let L be strictly convex in the \dot{x} direction and let*

L be strictly concave in the x direction. Let $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ everywhere in the (x, \dot{x}) space. Then every Euler-Lagrange curve will be periodic.

$\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ everywhere in the (x, \dot{x}) space imply that L is separated with respect to x and \dot{x} .

We have $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ along every Euler-Lagrange curve and the Euler-Lagrange condition gives $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ everywhere.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange equations $\begin{pmatrix} d\tilde{p} \\ d\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} d\dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} + dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ dt(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix}$ under the condition $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ can be expressed as:

$$(2.1) \quad \begin{pmatrix} d\tilde{p} \\ d\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = dt \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ \tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix}$$

The strictly convexity along the \dot{x} direction means $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} > 0$ everywhere, and the strictly concavity along the x direction means $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} < 0$ everywhere.

Figure 1 below shows a geometrical interpretation of some isolines in the (\dot{x}, \tilde{p}) space.

FIGURE 1

2.1. Situation A is tied to situation B for each step. We intend in this section to prove that the periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange curves with some period length T , depending of the curve, in a situation A imply the periodicity with period length T of the Euler-Lagrange curves in a situation B. The proof uses the differentials of the derivations in a geometric step by step reconstruction of the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation A to the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation B.

We define L_A to be an autonomous Lagrange function $L_A : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L_A \in C^3$ where $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} = 1$ and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = -1$. There is only one function that satisfies this and the function is: $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$. For this function will $\tilde{p}(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}}(x, \dot{x}) = \dot{x}$ and $\tilde{p}(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial x}(x, \dot{x}) = -x$.

We look at the L_A surface where we have that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} = 1$ and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = -1$. The Euler-Lagrange equations becomes

$$(2.2) \quad \begin{pmatrix} d\tilde{p} \\ d\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = dt \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x} \\ \tilde{p} \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 2 below shows a geometrical interpretation of some isolines for situation A .

FIGURE 2

We know that every Euler-Lagrange solution in the (x, \dot{x}) space is periodic for $L_A(x, \dot{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^2$.

We define L_B to be an autonomous Lagrange function $L_B : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L_B \in C^3$ where $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ is a function of \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = -1$.

We Look at the L_B surface where we have that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ is a function of \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = -1$. The Euler-Lagrange equations takes the form:

$$(2.3) \quad \begin{pmatrix} d\tilde{p} \\ d\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = dt \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{x} \\ \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 3 below shows a geometrical interpretation of some isolines for situation B .

FIGURE 3

We follow the Euler-Lagrange curve for situation B . First we follow the Euler-Lagrange curve forwards at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0)$ and backwards at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the \dot{x} direction.

We want to tie the situation A to B for each step. In situation A we also follow the Euler-Lagrange curve forwards at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0)$ and backwards at $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the \dot{x} direction.

We would like to assert that $\tilde{p}_A = \tilde{p}_B$ for each step. That is ensured by having $d\tilde{p}_A = d\tilde{p}_B$ for each step.

For each step the Euler-Lagrange equations give:

$$(2.4) \quad d\tilde{p}_A = dt_A(-\dot{x}_A)$$

$$(2.5) \quad d\dot{x}_A = dt_A \tilde{p}_A$$

$$(2.6) \quad d\tilde{p}_B = dt_B(-\dot{x}_B)$$

$$(2.7) \quad d\dot{x}_B = dt_B \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \tilde{p}_B$$

We have $d\tilde{p}_A = dt_A(-\dot{x}_A)$ and $d\tilde{p}_B = dt_B(-\dot{x}_B)$ so if we choose $dt_B = dt_A \frac{\dot{x}_A}{\dot{x}_B}$ will we have ensured that $d\tilde{p}_A = d\tilde{p}_B$ for each step.

The effect on $d\dot{x}_B$ is $d\dot{x}_B = dt_B \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \tilde{p}_B = dt_A \frac{\dot{x}_A}{\dot{x}_B} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \tilde{p}_B = dt_A \frac{\dot{x}_A}{\dot{x}_B} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \tilde{p}_A = \frac{\dot{x}_A}{\dot{x}_B} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} d\dot{x}_A$. That is:

$$(2.8) \quad d\dot{x}_B = \frac{\dot{x}_A}{\dot{x}_B} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} d\dot{x}_A$$

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation B is uniform in the \tilde{p} direction stretched in the \dot{x} direction compared to the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation A .

We know that in situation A there are the two Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0)$ and $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0)$ going to meet at $\tilde{p} = 0$. Because the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation B is uniformly in the \tilde{p} direction stretched in the \dot{x} direction compared to the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation A the curves in situation B also will have to meet at $\tilde{p} = 0$.

Following the Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = \tilde{p}_0)$ and $(\dot{x} = 0, \tilde{p} = -\tilde{p}_0)$ in the $-\dot{x}$ direction can be done analog to what we have showed above.

We see that the periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange curves of situation A imply the periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange curves of situation B .

Figure 4 below shows a geometrical interpretation of some isolines in a step and how they apply in situation A and B .

FIGURE 4

2.2. Situation B is tied to situation C for each step. We intend in this section to prove that the periodicity of the Euler-Lagrange curves with some period length T , depending on the curve, in a situation B imply the periodicity with period length T of the Euler-Lagrange curves in a situation C . The proof uses the differentials of the derivations in a geometric step by step reconstruction of the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation B to the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation C .

We define L_C to be an autonomous Lagrange function $L_C : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L_B \in C^3$ where $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ is a function of \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$ is a function of x .

We look at the L_C surface where we have that $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ is a function of \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$ is a function of x . In this case the Euler-Lagrange equations can be expressed as: $\begin{pmatrix} d\tilde{p} \\ d\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = dt \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix}$.

Figure 5 below reminds us of the isolines for situation C .

We follow the Euler-Lagrange curve for situation C . We do so by following the Euler-Lagrange curve forwards at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and backwards at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \tilde{p} direction.

We want to tie the situation B to C for each step. In situation B we also follow the Euler-Lagrange curve forwards at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and backwards at $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the \tilde{p} direction.

FIGURE 5

We would like to assert that $\dot{x}_{B_4} = \dot{x}_{C_4}$ and $\dot{x}_{B_1} = \dot{x}_{C_1}$ for each step. To do that we have to ensure that $d\dot{x}_{B_4} = d\dot{x}_{C_4}$ and $d\dot{x}_{B_1} = d\dot{x}_{C_1}$ for each step.

For each step the Euler-Lagrange equations gives:

$$(2.9) \quad d\tilde{p}_{B_4} = dt_{B_4}(-\dot{x}_{B_4})$$

$$(2.10) \quad d\dot{x}_{B_4} = dt_{B_4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \right)_1 \tilde{p}_{B_4}$$

$$(2.11) \quad d\hat{p}_{B_1} = dt_{B_1}(-\dot{x}_{B_1})$$

$$(2.12) \quad d\dot{x}_{B_1} = dt_{B_1} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}} \right)_1 \hat{p}_{B_1}$$

$$(2.13) \quad d\tilde{p}_{C_4} = dt_{C_4} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_4}$$

$$(2.14) \quad d\dot{x}_{C_4} = dt_{C_4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \right)_1 \tilde{p}_{C_4}$$

$$(2.15) \quad d\tilde{p}_{C_1} = dt_{C_1} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_1}$$

$$(2.16) \quad d\dot{x}_{C_1} = dt_{C_1} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \right)_1 \tilde{p}_{C_1}$$

We have $d\dot{x}_{B_4} = dt_{B_4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \right)_1 \tilde{p}_{B_4}$ and $d\dot{x}_{C_4} = dt_{C_4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \right)_1 \tilde{p}_{C_4}$. That imply that if we choose $dt_{C_4} = dt_{B_4} \frac{\tilde{p}_{B_4}}{\tilde{p}_{C_4}}$ is $d\dot{x}_1 = d\dot{x}_{C_4} = d\dot{x}_{B_4}$ ensured for each step.

We have $d\dot{x}_{B_1} = dt_{B_1} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}} \right)_1 \hat{p}_{B_1}$ and $d\dot{x}_{C_1} = dt_{C_1} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \hat{p}} \right)_1 \hat{p}_{C_1}$. That imply that if we choose $dt_{C_1} = dt_{B_1} \frac{\hat{p}_{B_1}}{\hat{p}_{C_1}}$ is $d\dot{x}_1 = d\dot{x}_{C_1} = d\dot{x}_{B_1}$ ensured for each step.

We would like to assert $\tilde{p}_B = \tilde{p}_{B_4} = \tilde{p}_{B_1}$ for each step. That can be ensured by having $d\tilde{p}_B = d\tilde{p}_{B_4} = d\tilde{p}_{B_1}$ for each step. We will have to choose suitable dt_{B_4} and dt_{B_1} to ensure that.

We have.

$$\begin{aligned} d\tilde{p}_{C_4} &= dt_{C_4} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_4} = dt_{B_4} \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_4}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_4} = dt_{B_4} \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_4}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{B_4} = -d\tilde{p}_B \\ &\quad \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_4}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \\ d\tilde{p}_{C_1} &= dt_{C_1} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_1} = dt_{B_1} \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_1}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{C_1} = dt_{B_1} \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_1}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \dot{x}_{B_1} = -d\tilde{p}_B \\ &\quad \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_1}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \end{aligned}$$

That is.

$$(2.17) \quad d\tilde{p}_{C_4} = -d\tilde{p}_B \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_4}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$$

$$(2.18) \quad d\tilde{p}_{C_1} = -d\tilde{p}_B \frac{\tilde{p}_B}{\tilde{p}_{C_1}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$$

That implies.

$$d\tilde{p}_{C_4} \tilde{p}_{C_4} = -d\tilde{p}_B \tilde{p}_B \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = d\tilde{p}_{C_1} \tilde{p}_{C_1} \quad \text{or} \quad d\tilde{p}_{C_4} \tilde{p}_{C_4} = d\tilde{p}_{C_1} \tilde{p}_{C_1}$$

The equation $d\tilde{p}_{C_4} \tilde{p}_{C_4} = d\tilde{p}_{C_1} \tilde{p}_{C_1}$ and $\tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} \neq 0$ implies that in the following steps in the construction is $d\tilde{p}_{C_4} = d\tilde{p}_{C_1}$.

For $\tilde{p}_C = \tilde{p}_{C_4} = \tilde{p}_{C_1} = 0$ we have the situation from which we started our transformation. These points don't change under the transformation.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation C is uniform in the x direction stretched in the \tilde{p} direction compared to the Euler-Lagrange curve in situation B . We know that in situation B are the two Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ going to meet at $\dot{x} = 0$, that implies that in situation C they also have to meet at $\dot{x} = 0$.

Following the Euler-Lagrange curves from $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{1,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ and $(\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{4,0}, \tilde{p} = 0)$ in the $-\tilde{p}$ direction can be done analog to what we have showed above.

Because the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation B are periodic and situation B is tied to C the Euler-Lagrange curves in situation C will also be periodic.

Figure 6 below shows a geometrical interpretation of some isolines in a step and how they apply in situation B and C .

FIGURE 6

The Euler-Lagrange curves in situation C covers the convex area α .”□”

2.3. Proof that the Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic. We intend in this chapter to prove that every Euler-Lagrange curve is periodic for some variable T under some conditions. We further more give an geometrical interpretation of the proof.

2.3.1. *Rewriting the Euler-Lagrange equation.*

PROPOSITION 12. *Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^2$. let L be strictly convex w.r.t \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} > 0$, let L be strictly concave w.r.t x and let L be non separated w.r.t. x*

and \dot{x} in the set V then is $(\partial_{\tilde{p}-\partial\dot{x}}^{\tilde{p}}) = dt(\frac{\dot{x}\frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}}{(\tilde{p}-\dot{x}\frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x})\frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}}})$ an Euler-Lagrange equations in the set V along an Euler-Lagrange curve.

That L is non separated w.r.t. x and \dot{x} is different from the constrains on L we have previously introduced. Under this constrain will we have that $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x}$ is not 0 everywhere in the set V

We remember that along an Euler-Lagrange curve will we have $\frac{d}{dt}(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) = \tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$.

We have defined \tilde{p} and \check{p} as functions of x and \dot{x} . Along an Euler-Lagrange curve in V will:

$$(2.19) \quad \frac{d\tilde{p}}{dt}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \frac{d\dot{x}(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$(2.20) \quad \frac{d\check{p}}{dt}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \frac{\partial x(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \frac{\partial \dot{x}(t)}{dt} \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

We can write these equations as:

$$(2.21) \quad \check{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$(2.22) \quad \check{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

We remember that $\frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) > 0$, the first equation can be written as $\ddot{x}(t) = (\check{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$.

This gives, along an Euler-Lagrange curve:

$$(2.23) \quad \ddot{x}(t) = (\check{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) - \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

$$(2.24) \quad \check{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = \dot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial x}(x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \ddot{x}(t) \frac{\partial\check{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$$

We have

$$\begin{pmatrix} \partial\check{p} \\ \partial\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} dt(\dot{x}(\frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) + \tilde{p} \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \\ dt(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \partial\check{p} \\ \partial\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} dt(\dot{x}(\frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) + \tilde{p} \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \\ dt(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix} \iff \\ \begin{pmatrix} \partial\check{p} \\ \partial\dot{x} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} dt(\dot{x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x} + \tilde{p} \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \\ dt(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial\tilde{p}}{\partial x}) \frac{\partial\dot{x}}{\partial\tilde{p}} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= dt \left(\begin{array}{c} (\dot{x} + \dot{\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= dt \left(\begin{array}{c} (\dot{x} + (\dot{\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} - \dot{x}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= dt \left(\begin{array}{c} (\dot{x} + ((\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= dt \left(\begin{array}{c} ((\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}) \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ 0 \end{array} \right) + dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ 0 \end{array} \right) + dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ 0 \end{array} \right) + dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} + dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ dt (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) \iff \\
(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) &= dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

□

We remember that the Euler-Lagrange equations rely on $\frac{d}{dt}(\tilde{p}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))) = \dot{\tilde{p}}(x(t), \dot{x}(t))$ to apply along an Euler-Lagrange curve.

REMARK 11. Because we have that $\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} \neq 0$ everywhere in V is $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \neq 0$ everywhere in V

2.3.2. *Geometrical considerations.* We have the Euler-Lagrange condition: $(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) = dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right)$. As introduced in the previous section.

We have seen that for $\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial x} = 0$ becomes the Euler-Lagrange condition $(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) = dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ \dot{\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right)$. As shown in chapter 4.

Now we wish to prove the same theorem as proofed in chapter 4, but with the L is separated with respect to x and \dot{x} condition removed.

The Euler-Lagrange condition $(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} + dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ dt (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right)$ can be written as:

$$(\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} + dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ dt (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) = dt \left(\begin{array}{c} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ \dot{\tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ -dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}} \end{array} \right)$$

We will show how this equation fits together on figure 10 below

The terms $\partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}$ and $-dt \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}$ also describe how the $\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}$ isoline (horizontal) and the $\frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}$ isoline (vertical) deviate from horizontal and

vertical. $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}$ tells us that by moving $\partial \tilde{x}$ we move $\partial \tilde{p}$ by $\partial \tilde{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \partial \tilde{p}$, this is identical to the term $\partial \tilde{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}$. By moving $\partial \tilde{p}$ we move $\partial x = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}} = \partial \tilde{p} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \tilde{p}}$. By moving ∂x we move $\partial \tilde{p} = \partial x \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$. By moving $\partial \tilde{p}$ we move $\partial \tilde{x} = \partial \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$, we have $\partial \tilde{x} = \partial \tilde{p} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$, or $\partial \tilde{x} = \partial x \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$. This is our term $-dt \tilde{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$. We can't do $\partial \tilde{p} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$, because be $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}$ extended to $\partial \tilde{p}$. This is illustrated on figure 11 below.

We can also see how values of the original vertical and horizontal $\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}$ isoline and $\frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}$ isoline are scaled. We have that $\frac{-dt \tilde{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{-dt \tilde{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \tilde{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \tilde{x}}$,

and $\frac{\partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{dt \dot{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}} = \frac{\partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$. The scale factor is $1 - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}} = \frac{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}{\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x}}$.

2.3.3. The Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system.

PROPOSITION 13. Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^2$. let L be strictly convex w.r.t \dot{x} and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x} \partial \dot{x}} = \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} > 0$, let L be strictly concave w.r.t x and let L be non separated

w.r.t. x and \dot{x} in the set V then is $(\frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right)$ an

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) = dt \left(\frac{\frac{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}} \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{1}{\frac{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}} (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}}} \right) \iff$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right) \iff$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}}\right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial (\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial x}}{(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right)$$

That works. See illustration below

We have

$$\partial(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}) = \partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \dot{x} \partial \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} = \partial \dot{\tilde{p}} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}} - \partial x \frac{\partial \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{dt}$$

We assume that $\partial x \frac{\partial \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{dt} = 0$, $\frac{\partial \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{dt}$ is in general not 0. However the contribution of $\partial x \frac{\partial \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{dt}$ becomes 0 when summarized.

We see that the Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\frac{\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system on a small scale has the same direction as the Euler-Lagrange curve in the $(\dot{\tilde{p}} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system, the length of a small vector is just changed with a factor of $\frac{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}} \frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\frac{\partial \dot{\tilde{p}}}{\partial x}}$. We can change the size of dt by multiplying it with a finite factor and not change the

solution. This tells us that in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})$ coordinate system will both of the following equations be Euler-Lagrange curves:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{p} - \partial \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}} \right) \text{ and } \left(\frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right).$$

We have that $\left(\frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right)$ is an Euler-Lagrange

curves in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system. \square

THEOREM 5. *Let L be an autonomous Lagrange function $L : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, $L \in C^3$, let L be strictly convex in the \dot{x} direction and let L be strictly concave in the x direction. Then will every Euler-Lagrange curve be periodic.*

We have that $\left(\frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial (\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}{\partial \dot{x}}}{(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}) \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial f(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}})}} \right)$ is an Euler-Lagrange

curves in the $(\tilde{p} - \dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}, \dot{x})$ coordinate system. We see that the solution has the same form as $\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = dt \left(\frac{\dot{x} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial \dot{x}}}{\tilde{p} \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial \tilde{p}}} \right)$ in the (\tilde{p}, \dot{x}) coordinate system and is therefor always periodic. \square

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